

International Conference on Development and Environmental Economics: SANDEE@25

Abstracts and Programmes

**Hotel Himalaya, Kathmandu, Nepal
12–14 December 2025**

About SANDEE

The South Asian Network for Development and Environmental Economics (SANDEE) is a research capacity and academic leadership development network of the International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development (ICIMOD) that uses economic tools and analyses to address environmental challenges that the region has been facing. SANDEE supports ICIMOD's programmatic work and strengthens its economic and policy analysis, provides research and technical support, and offers mentorship to young researchers for enhancing their research capacity and academic leadership. Established in 1999, it works in ten countries in South Asia and the Hindu Kush Himalaya (HKH) region: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, China, India, Maldives, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka.

About the conference

In celebration of its 25 years of service to the region, SANDEE is organising the 'International Conference on Development and Environmental Economics: SANDEE@25'.

The theme of the conference is 'development, environment, and mountains' with the key areas being biodiversity, climate, ecosystems, environmental pollution, forest restoration, livelihoods, and mountains and people.

South Asia, in general, and the HKH region, in particular, are facing escalating and severe impacts from climate change, biodiversity loss, and pollution. In this context, socio-economic challenges, including inequality, poverty, unemployment, population growth, rapid urbanisation, and land use changes, are among the most pressing issues. At the conference, leading researchers from the HKH region and beyond will share insights to aid governments, policymakers, and communities in understanding and addressing these pressing challenges.

The conference features three distinguished scholars as the keynote speakers, alongside several engaging panels and parallel sessions.

Message from the Conference Organising Committee Chair and Co-Chairs

It is our privilege to welcome you to the 'International Conference on Development and Environmental Economics: SANDEE@25', as we celebrate 25 years of SANDEE in research capacity building and academic leadership development across South Asia and, more recently, the Hindu Kush Himalaya (HKH) region. The past two and a half decades of SANDEE's efforts have nurtured a culture of collaboration and cooperation among the researchers across the region. It continues its commitment to build a vibrant community of scholars dedicated to advancing environmental economics research, teaching, and policy engagement. What began as a modest regional initiative in 1999 has, in the last 25 years, evolved into an influential network that has impacted academia and policy from grassroots to cross-country levels. SANDEE's research is distinguished by being locally grounded with a rigorous evidence base. The research emanating from the network aspires to be at the forefront of the knowledge curve and shape a new generation of environmental economists in the region who inspire innovation in times of climate change.

This milestone conference reflects the intellectual depth and diversity that SANDEE has cultivated over the years. The programme includes three keynote lectures by globally renowned experts addressing some of today's most pressing challenges that resonate strongly with SANDEE's long-standing focus on policy-relevant research – measuring natural capital for sustainability, managing the commons in rapidly changing socio-ecological systems, and adaptation in the age of climate change.

In addition, seven special panels that complement the keynotes and explore a rich set of contemporary issues. These include: (a) reflections, recollections, and future directions of SANDEE; b) the role of research networks in addressing sustainability challenges, (c) implementing payment for ecosystem services, (d) managing natural resources in an era of uncertainty, (e) harnessing big data and digital technology for sustainable economic development, (f) water security in mountain regions, and (g) the dynamics of the energy transition. Together, these panels highlight the breadth of conversations shaping the future of research in environmental economics in the region.

The conference further features over 70 research papers presented across 20 parallel sessions, encompassing an extensive array of themes. These include technology and sustainability in agriculture, climate policies and livelihoods, environmental sustainability and environmental health, forest conservation, management and livelihoods, environmental valuation and governance, household energy choices, climate change and agriculture, water and forest management, gender and the energy transition, environmental pollution, climate adaptation and mitigation, natural disasters, and other emerging areas within environmental and development economics. This thematic diversity underscores the complexity of sustainability challenges across South Asia and the HKH, and the vitality of the research community working to address them.

While not all of SANDEE's research network members could attend the conference, their continuing efforts make us proud. Those who could join us at the conference have contributed an abstract to this volume. It embodies the passion, analytical rigour, and dedication of researchers who have shaped and continue to strengthen SANDEE's enduring legacy. Their work not only advances academic discourse but also provides crucial insights for policymakers, practitioners, and communities navigating environmental and developmental changes.

We extend our heartfelt appreciation to the keynote speakers, panellists, authors, reviewers, the advisory, organising, and scientific committees, our partner institutions, funding partners, ICIMOD's Regional Member Countries (RMCs), and the entire conference team whose commitment and hard work have made this event possible. This gathering stands as a testament

to the power of shared purpose, regional collaboration, and collective effort for addressing the pressing challenges of the region.

As we commemorate this milestone, we are reminded of the urgent challenges confronting our region, from accelerating climate vulnerability to evolving energy and livelihood transitions, from environmental degradation to governance gaps. We firmly believe that SANDEE@25 will reinvigorate the collective ambition of our research community to confront these challenges with renewed creativity, rigour, and partnership. The knowledge shared and relationships forged at the conference will help guide SANDEE's next chapter and strengthen its role in supporting and promoting evidence-based decision-making for a sustainable future.

We wish you an insightful, engaging, and truly memorable conference experience.

Izabella Koziell

Deputy Director General,
ICIMOD, Nepal
Chair, Organising Committee

Pranab Mukhopadhyay

Senior Professor, Goa
University, India
Co-Chair, Organising Committee

Mani Nepal

Senior Programme Coordinator,
SANDEE, ICIMOD, Nepal
Co-Chair, Organising Committee

Keynote speakers

Sir Partha Dasgupta

**Frank Ramsey Professor Emeritus of Economics
Cambridge University, UK**

Sir Partha Dasgupta is the Frank Ramsey Professor Emeritus in Economics at Cambridge University, Fellow of St John's College, Cambridge, and Director of the Darwin-Hamied Centre for Biodiversity and Demography at Christ's College, Cambridge. He has also taught at the London School of Economics, London, UK and Stanford University, California, USA. Dasgupta is the first economist to be elected a Fellow of the Royal Society in the UK. Along with Karl-Göran Mäler of Sweden, he co-founded SANDEE. Additionally, Dasgupta is a foreign member of the US National Academy of Sciences, the American Academy of Arts and Sciences, American Philosophical Society, and the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, and is an honorary fellow of the London School of Economics and Trinity College (Cambridge). He has received the Volvo Environment Prize (2002), John Kenneth Galbraith Prize (2006), Zayed International Environment Prize (2011), Blue Planet Prize (2015), Tyler Prize (2016), the 2021 Kew International Medal of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, UK, and the BBVA Foundation Frontiers of Knowledge Award. He has been awarded honorary doctorates by Harvard University, USA; Wageningen University, Netherlands; University of Bologna, Italy; Tilburg University, Netherlands; Catholic University of Louvain, Belgium, and University of York, UK. His latest works include two independent reviews, 'The Economics of Biodiversity: The Dasgupta Review (2024)' and 'On Natural Capital: The Value of the World Around Us' (forthcoming, 2025).

Ruth Meinzen-Dick

**Research Fellow Emeritus,
International Food Policy Research Institute, USA**

Ruth Meinzen-Dick is a Research Fellow Emeritus at the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI). Her work concentrates on two main (and occasionally interconnected) areas: the impact of institutions on how people manage natural resources and the role of gender in development processes. This has led her to study land and water policy, property rights, collective action and other governance arrangements, games for experiential learning, and the impact of development interventions, drawing on fieldwork in South Asia and Africa.

Ruth is the past president of the International Association for Study of the Commons (IASC), USA, and a recipient of the Elinor Ostrom Collective Governance of the Commons 2019 Senior Scholar Award. She holds a PhD in development sociology from Cornell University, USA.

**Adil Najam, President
Worldwide Fund for Nature (WWF) International; Dean
Emeritus and Professor, Boston University, USA**

Adil Najam is Dean Emeritus and Professor of International Relations and Earth and Environment at the Frederick S Pardee School of Global Studies, Boston University, Boston, USA. He previously served as Vice-Chancellor of Lahore University of Management Sciences (LUMS) in Lahore, Pakistan, and the Director of the Boston University Pardee Center for the Study of the Longer-Range Future, USA. Adil has also taught at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), USA, and the Fletcher School of Law and Diplomacy, Tufts University, USA.

He was a lead author for the third and fourth assessments of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and has written over 100 scholarly papers and book chapters. Adil is a former trustee of the International Board of World Wildlife Fund (WWF) International (2011–2019) and has served on multiple other boards, including the as chair of the Luc Hoffmann Institute and South Asian Network of Development and Environmental Economics. He has frequently served as advisor to international organisations, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and governments.

**Biswo Nath Poudel
Governor, Nepal Rastra Bank, Nepal**

Biswo Poudel is the governor of Nepal Rastra Bank. He had also served as professor at Kathmandu University, Vice Chairperson of the National Planning Commission, Chairperson of the Board of Governors of ICIMOD, President of Colombo Plan Council and chair of the Regional Economic Cooperation and Integration (RECI) in Asia and the Pacific. Dr Poudel earned a PhD in Agriculture and Resource Economics from the University of California at Berkeley, USA. His articles have been published in the American Journal of Agricultural Economics, Natural Resources Modelling, Journal of Agricultural and Applied Economics, Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy, and Applied Economics Letters. He was also a regular columnist for the Kantipur Daily in Nepal and has appeared in many popular podcasts.

Committee Chairs

Advisory Committee Chair

Pema Gyamtsho,
Director General, ICIMOD, Nepal

Pema Gyamtsho joined ICIMOD as Director General in October 2020. He is the first Director General from the region that ICIMOD serves since its establishment in 1983. Prior to joining ICIMOD, he served in the Royal Government of Bhutan for over three decades, holding positions in natural resources management and planning, rural development, agriculture, forestry, livestock and food production, rangeland management, livestock development, participatory approaches, research and extension institutional building, climate change and environmental protection, biodiversity conservation, and organic farming.

Pema was Deputy Secretary of Bhutan's Ministry of Agriculture and Forests from 1998 to 2002, where he was responsible for policy and planning. From 2002 to 2006, he worked at ICIMOD, initially leading policy and partnerships work, then taking up the centre's regional rangeland management work. He then joined Helvetas/Swiss Development Corporation as Deputy Resident Coordinator, a position he held from 2006 to 2007.

In 2008, he returned to government office in Bhutan, serving as Minister of Agriculture and Forests till 2013. In this role, he led over 4,000 staff working in the agriculture, livestock, forestry and environment sectors. His roles ran from the senior-most level of decision-making in Bhutan – where he shaped and often led the enactment of over 60 pieces of legislation – to the grassroots level where he oversaw the formation of over 400 farmers' groups and cooperatives. He also led Bhutan's delegation to COP15 in Denmark in 2009, where he deposited Bhutan's instrument to remain carbon neutral, making it one of the first declarations of its kind. Between 2013 and 2020, he was a member of the National Assembly of Bhutan.

Pema holds a PhD in natural sciences from the Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich, Switzerland, and an MSc in agriculture from Lincoln University, New Zealand.

Scientific Committee Chair

Eswaran Somanathan
Professor, Indian Statistical Institute Delhi, India

Eswaran Somanathan is a professor in the Economics and Planning Unit of the Indian Statistical Institute in Delhi and the founding head of the Centre for Research on the Economics of Climate, Food, Energy, and Environment (CECFEE), India, a policy-relevant research centre at the institute. He received his PhD in economics from Harvard University, USA. His research is in the economics of environment, development, and politics. Some of his recent works are about household air pollution, groundwater depletion, climate impacts, and carbon pricing. He has served on various committees of the Government of India on environmental policy. A fellow of the Bureau for Research and Economic Analysis of Development (BREAD) and SANDEE, he was a coordinating lead author for the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). He is a co-editor of the journal *Environment and Development Economics* published by Cambridge University Press.

Organising Committee Chair

Izabella Koziell

Deputy Director General, ICIMOD, Nepal

Izabella Koziell has served as Deputy Director General of ICIMOD since 2021. She is the first woman in ICIMOD's history to hold the position of Deputy Director General.

Izabella oversees the programmatic portfolio at ICIMOD, led the development of the organisation's Strategy 2030: Moving Mountains and the formulation of the Medium-Term Action Plan 2023–26, and is committed to increasing the pace at which the organisation delivers results.

Before joining ICIMOD, she worked in multiple leadership and management positions in various international organisations, working on the interconnected risks presented by climate, environment, biodiversity, and development, primarily for the Global South. Her previous positions have included 5 years as Director for a cross-CGIAR programme around Water, Land and Ecosystems at the International Water Management Institute in Sri Lanka, 15 years with the UK Department for International Development (DFID, now FCDO) in a variety of policy and programming positions. She has also worked for the International Institute for Environment and Development (IIED), UK, where she led some of the early work linking biodiversity with development, having begun her career in dryland Tanzania working with farmers and pastoralists with the Lutheran World Service.

Organising Committee Co-Chair

Pranab Mukhopadhyay

Professor, Goa University, India

Pranab Mukhopadhyay is Professor of Economics and Vice-Dean (Research) at the Goa Business School at Goa University, India. He is a fellow of SANDEE and the Indian Society for Ecological Economics (INSEE), and formerly President of INSEE (2016–18). Earlier, he worked as an environmental economist for the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), Nepal. He is the current editor of Ecology, Economy, and Society – the INSEE Journal. His research interests include managing commons, nature and society, sustainable development, ecosystem services, and economic growth. Pranab studied economics at Presidency College, Calcutta and Jawaharlal Nehru University, India.

Organising Committee Co-Chair

Mani Nepal

Senior Programme Coordinator, SANDEE, ICIMOD, Nepal

Mani Nepal has served as Programme Coordinator of SANDEE and Lead Economist for ICIMOD since 2018, having previously worked as SANDEE's Senior Environmental Economist and Research Programme Manager.

He has a long history of working in academia, working as a distinguished visiting professor at Kyoto University, Japan; Adjunct Professor at Agriculture and Forestry University, Visiting Professor at Kathmandu University, and Associate Professor at Tribhuvan University, Nepal; and Visiting Assistant Professor at the University of New Mexico, USA.

He also held a Senior Economist position at the Department of Finance and Administration, Santa Fe, New Mexico, USA.

Mani is an applied economist with research interest at the intersection of development and environmental issues, where his research outcomes are published in highly visible international journals such as the American Journal of Political Science, Journal of Conflict Resolutions, Environmental and Resource Economics, Ecological Economics, Journal of Forest Economics, PLOS One, Scientific Reports – a nature portfolio journal, Environment and Development Economics, Land Economics, Ecology and Society, Environmental Research Letters, and World Development, among others.

His latest work includes an edited volume, "[Climate Change, and Community Resilience: Insights from South Asia](#)".

Mani received a PhD in Economics and Applied Econometrics from the University of New Mexico, USA, and is a Fulbright Scholar who received an MS degree in Policy Economics from the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, USA.

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All timestamps are in Nepal Standard Time (NPT)

Programme summary	
Time (NPT)	Day 01, Friday, 12 December 2025
08:30–09:00	Registration
09:00–10:30	Dissemination workshop on ‘Economics of forest restoration as carbon mitigation and Nature-based Solutions in South Asia’ Moderator: Mani Nepal (Open for all SANDEE@25 participants) Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room
10:30–11:00	Photo session Tea/coffee break
11:00–12:30	Panel discussion on ‘Economics of forest restoration as carbon mitigation and Nature-based Solutions in South Asia’ Moderator: Soumya Balasubramanya (Open for all SANDEE@25 participants) Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room
12:30–13:30	Lunch
13:30–14:00	Opening Remarks: Mani Nepal Welcome Remarks: Pema Gyamtsho Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room
14:00–15:30	Natural capital and the meaning of sustainable development Founder's keynote by Sir Partha Dasgupta , Frank Ramsey Professor Emeritus of Economics, Cambridge University Moderator: Subhrendu Pattanayak Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room
15:30 – 15:40	Book launch SANDEE@25: Reflections, lessons and memories of collective growth
15:40–16:15	Photo session Tea/coffee break
16:15–17:45	Reflections panel Moderator: David Potter Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room
17:45–18:00	SANDEE evaluation and tracer survey results: Ghulam Muhammad Shah Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room
18:30–20:30	Reception dinner

Time (NPT)	Day 02 Saturday, 13 December 2025
08:30–09:00	Registration
09:00–10:15	<p>Our common(s) heritage: Contributions of development and environmental economics Keynote by Ruth Meinzen-Dick, Senior Research Fellow Emeritus, IFPRI Moderator: E Somanathan Hall name: Himalaya Grand Ball Room</p>
10:15–11:00	<p>Bank lending in agricultural sector in Nepal: Issues and opportunities Keynote by Biswo Nath Poudel, Governor, Nepal Rastra Bank Moderator: Mani Nepal Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room</p>
11:00–11:15	Tea/coffee break
11:15–12:45	<p>Panel A1 Knowledge networks in times of climate change Moderator: Pranab Mukhopadhyay Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room</p>
	<p>Panel A2 Potential for scaling electric cooking in Nepal Moderator: E. Somanathan Hall: Rato Baithak</p>
	<p>Panel A3 Innovative financing for mountain ecosystem services: Strengthening payment for ecosystem services (PES) mechanisms Moderator: Shweta Bhagwat Hall: Skyline</p>
12:45–13:30	Lunch
13:30–15:00	Parallel sessions A1 - A5
15:00–15:30	Tea/coffee break
15:30–17:00	Parallel sessions B1 - B5

Time (NPT)	Day 03, Sunday, 14 December 2025
08:30–09:00	Registration
09:00–10:30	Living in the age of adaptation: New challenges and new responsibilities for knowledge Keynote by Adil Najam , President, Worldwide Fund for Nature; Professor, Boston University Moderator: Jeffrey Vincent Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room
10:30–10:45	Vote of thanks By David Potter Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room
10:45–11:00	Tea/coffee break
11:00–12:30	Panel B1 The economics of springshed management and springs restoration in the HKH Moderator: Sarala Khaling Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room
	Panel B2 Harnessing big data and digital technologies for economic development in the HKH Moderator: Birendra Bajracharya Hall: Rato Baithak
	Panel B3 Landscape resource conservation for improving water availability, building climate resilience, and strengthening ecosystem services: Evidence from India Moderator: S. Madheswaran Hall: Skyline
12:30–13:30	Lunch
13:30–15:00	Parallel sessions C1 - C5
15:00–15:30	Tea/coffee break
15:30–17:00	Parallel sessions D1 - D5

Keynote abstracts

DAY 01

Friday, 12 December 2025 | 14:00–15:30

Natural capital and the meaning of sustainable development

Speaker

Sir Partha Dasgupta,

Frank Ramsey Professor Emeritus of Economics, Cambridge University, UK

Moderator

Subhrendu K. Pattanayak,

Oak Foundation Distinguished Professor of Environmental and Energy Policy, Duke University, USA

Abstract

The Brundtland Commission very sensibly defined sustainable development (SD) as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” My own work of 2000, joint with Karl-Göran Mäler, was to find an operational criterion for the idea. Instead of referring to ‘needs’, Mäler and I spoke about intergenerational well-being, and defined SD as any programme of consumption and accumulation that is associated with non-declining well-being across the generations. And we showed that this requirement is equivalent to the requirement that an inclusive value of wealth is non-declining. The qualifier ‘inclusive’ (others, such as Kenneth Arrow, subsequently called it ‘comprehensive’) is invoked to stress that natural capital is included in the notion of wealth. It will be noticed that SD is not uniquely given – there are potentially an infinite number of SD programmes for an economy, but the requirement does prune out those development paths along which well-being across the generations would dip from time to time. So, the criterion offers a partial ordering of economic programmes. Notice also that the equivalence between intergenerational well-being and inclusive wealth speaks to an equivalence between human ends (well-being) and a set of means (wealth) to those ends. Therein lies its analytical substance. There is now a substantial applied literature, comparing the inclusive wealth of nations across time. The research was initiated at IHDP/UNEP by Anantha Duraiappah and his colleagues in ‘The Inclusive Wealth Report, 2012’, and has been developed further at the World Bank.

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 09:00–10:15

Our common(s) heritage: Contributions of development and environmental economics

Speaker

Ruth Meinzen-Dick

Senior Research Fellow, International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), USA

Moderator

E. Somanathan

Professor, Economics and Planning Unit, Indian Statistical Institute, India

Abstract

The past 25 years have seen a burgeoning of research on the commons – shared natural resources such as forests, rangelands, and water systems. A recent report drawing on 161 studies of the value of ecosystem services was able to estimate the value of commons in India at US\$90.5 billion, raising attention to the importance of these resources that are often considered ‘wastelands’. But such benefits do not arise from nature alone: they depend on human institutions that support investment in, and benefit sharing from the commons. This presentation will particularly discuss advances in understanding of the roles of tenure and governance in the management of commons, and how research on these topics has influenced policy and programs. It will highlight the contributions of development and environmental economics, as well as expanding transdisciplinary work on the commons, including innovative work on the use of games as interventions to strengthen equitable commons management. The talk will conclude with future directions for research on shared resources.

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 10:15–11:00

Bank lending in the agricultural sector in Nepal: Issues and opportunities

Speaker

Biswo Nath Poudel

Governor, Nepal Rastra Bank, Nepal

Moderator

Mani Nepal

ICIMOD, Nepal

Abstract

Access to credit is often cited as an important barrier to growth for farmers. In this talk, Governor Poudel chronicles the growth of the agricultural sector credit in Nepal as it evolves using different lending methods. While agriculture sector credits have been provided using cooperatives, specialised agricultural banks, commercial banks, and microfinance institutes (MFIs), often in combination with government subsidies, their effectiveness on agriculture output and farmer welfare is not clear. In the absence of other supporting financial instruments such as insurance and options, in times of economic difficulties, farmers' welfare may decrease even when agricultural output increases.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 09:00–10:30

Living in the age of adaptation: New challenges and new responsibilities for knowledge

Speaker

Adil Najam

President, Worldwide Fund for Nature (WWF) International;
Professor and Dean Emeritus, Boston University, USA

Moderator

Jeffrey Vincent

Clarence F Korstian Professor of Forest Economics and Management,
Nicholas School of the Environment, Duke University, USA

Abstract

Because the world has been unwilling and unable to respond to the threat of global climate change in time with appropriate measures of mitigation, we are now condemned to live in the ‘Age of Adaptation.’ Adaptation, after all, is essentially the failure of mitigation. This does not mean that the need to mitigate has gone away – the less we mitigate today, the more we will have to adapt to the impacts of climate change tomorrow. This does, however, mean that dealing with the impacts and consequences of climate change is no longer a ‘future’ challenge. It is a pressing and immediate challenge – most so in the highly vulnerable regions of South Asia, which are economically impoverished and climatically imperilled.

The talk will explore (a) how we came upon the Age of Adaptation; (b) what it means to live in the Age of Adaptation; (c) what the Age of Adaptation means for South Asia particularly in relation to issues like water, food, and security; and (d) it will posit that all of the above raises a whole new set of challenges – and also new responsibilities – for scholars and researchers who work on environment and development.

Panel abstracts

DAY 01

Friday, 12 December 2025 | 16:15–17:45

SANDEE@25 Years: Reflections, recollections, and future directions

Moderator

David Potter

Head of Regional Action and Global Advocacy, ICIMOD, Nepal

Panellists

- **Bishwambher Pyakuryal**, Professor, Tribhuvan University; President, Nepal Economic Association, Nepal
- **Eklabya Sharma**, former Deputy Director General, ICIMOD; Strategic Advisor and Director of The Himalaya Initiative, Ashoka Trust for Research in Ecology and the Environment (ATREE), India
- **A. K. Enamul Haque**, Professor and Director General, Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies (BIDS), Bangladesh; SANDEE Advisor
- **Joyashree Roy**, Distinguished Professor and Founder Director: South and South-East Asia Multidisciplinary Applied Research Network on Transforming Societies of Global South (SMARTS), Asian Institute of Technology, Thailand; former grantee.
- **Prabath Nisantha Edirisinghe**, Director General, Forest Department of Sri Lanka, Sri Lanka; former Grantee
- **Tehmina Mangan**, Vice Chancellor and Professor, The Begum Nusrat Bhutto Women University Sukkur, Pakistan; former Grantee
- **Jeffrey R. Vincent**, Clarence F. Korstian Professor of Forest Economics & Management, Nicholas School of the Environment, Duke University, USA; SANDEE Advisor.

In celebration of its 25 years of service to the region, the South Asian Network for Development and Environmental Economics (SANDEE) of the International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development (ICIMOD) is organising the International Conference on Development and Environmental Economics: SANDEE@25, to be held in Kathmandu, Nepal, from 12–14 December 2025. On this milestone occasion, this panel brings together individuals, including grantees, who have contributed to SANDEE in various capacities, some since its inception, to share their reflections and experiences about SANDEE.

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 11:15–12:45

Panel A1 | Knowledge networks in the times of climate change

Moderator:

Pranab Mukhopadhyay,
Senior Professor, Goa University, India

Panellists

- **Ken-Ichi Akao**, Professor, School of Social Sciences, Waseda University; President of Asian Association of Environmental and Resource Economics (AAERE), India
- **Orapan Srisawalak**, Associate Professor, Sukhothai Thammathirat Open University, Thailand; Longtime Environment and Economy Programme of South East Asia (EEPSEA) associate and resource person
- **Seema Purushothaman**, President, Indian Society for Ecological Economics (INSEE), India
- **Gunnar Köhlin**, Director, Environment for Development (Efd), Sweden
- **Bhim Adhikari**, Senior Program Specialist, International Development Research Centre (IDRC), Canada
- **AnnaMaria Oltorp**, Head of the Development Cooperation Section, Regional Asia and the Pacific, of the Swedish Embassy in Bangkok, Thailand
- **Mani Nepal**, Senior Program Coordinator, SANDEE, ICIMOD, Nepal

Abstract

Regional collaboration has become essential for addressing environmental and developmental challenges that transcend political boundaries. Issues such as climate change, resource degradation, and ecological resilience demand shared data, comparative analysis, and collective policy responses. In this context, regional research networks play a vital role in building capacity, harmonising methodologies, and fostering dialogue between researchers and policymakers. Over the years, they have also helped nurture communities of practice that span institutions and countries. This panel brings together leaders of regional and global networks from across the world to reflect on how such networks can, and have, strengthened both the scientific and policy dimensions of (environmental) research. We will explore how collaboration across institutions and regions can, and already does, generate more inclusive, policy-relevant, and innovative insights into the economics of sustainability. In doing so, these networks can help countries design better incentives, institutions, and investments to tackle environmental and developmental challenges that cross borders. Our goal is to draw lessons from diverse experiences, identify good practices, and envision a stronger, more connected research ecosystem for the region.

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 11:15–12:45

Panel A2 | Potential for scaling electric cooking in Nepal

Moderator

E. Somanathan

Professor, Economics and Planning Unit, Indian Statistical Institute, India

Panellists

- **Praveen Kumar**, Post Doc Fellow, Ashoka University, India
- **Eshita Gupta**, Technical Director, KPMG India
- **Karuna Bajracharya**, Country Director Nepal, Clean Cooking Alliance, Nepal
- **Nawa Raj Dhakal**, Executive Director, Alternative Energy Promotion Centre, Government of Nepal
- **Subarna Kapali**, Managing Director, Ajummary Bikas Foundation (P) Ltd, Nepal

Abstract

This session examines the potential for scaling electric cooking in Nepal using household-level evidence and implementation experience, complemented by comparative insights from Kerala, India. It will consider how electric cooking fits within Nepal's clean energy transition landscape, national energy strategy, climate commitments, and broader development goals. Speakers will discuss the design and use of monitoring and evaluation frameworks to generate actionable evidence and improve programme design, as well as the main constraints to scale electric cooking, including affordability, infrastructure, reliability, and behavioural change. Bringing together energy economists, a clean-cooking specialist, policymakers, and practitioners, the session will focus on exploring practical pathways for wider adoption of electric cooking. These include enabling a regulatory environment, targeted support instruments, and partnership models, and identifying concrete, evidence-based options for advancing inclusive and efficient electric cooking solutions in Nepal.

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 11:15–12:45

Panel A3 | Innovative financing for mountain ecosystem services: Strengthening PES mechanisms

Moderator:

Shweta Bhagwat,

Senior Specialist– Nature-based Solutions and Climate Finance,
IORA Ecological Solutions, India

Panellists

- **Pyush Dogra**, Senior Environmental Specialist, Environment, Natural Resources & Blue Economy (ENB) Global Practice, The World Bank, New Delhi, India
- **Akriti Wanchoo**, Vice President– Agriculture and Climate Change, Iora Ecological Solutions, New Delhi, India
- **Priyamvada Bagaria**, Senior Manager, Ecosystem Services, Iora Ecological Solutions, New Delhi, India
- **Ritesh Sharma**, Intervention Manager - Incentives (Natural Resource Economist), ICIMOD, Nepal
- **Saudamini Das**, Professor in Economics, Institute of Economic Growth, Delhi, India

Abstract

Mountain ecosystems in the Hindu Kush Himalaya (HKH) region provide critical services like carbon sequestration, watershed protection, biodiversity conservation, and cultural significance, supporting millions of livelihoods. However, financing for these services through Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) remains insufficient. This panel will explore innovative financial models to strengthen PES, ensuring sustainability and equitable benefit-sharing. It emphasises cultural ecosystem services and indigenous knowledge, integrating them into conservation practices for the HKH region. The panel will unite academics, policymakers, private sector actors, NGOs, and indigenous leaders to discuss scalable, inclusive PES frameworks, offering actionable solutions for SANDEE's community. Overall, the session aims to identify actionable strategies, opportunities for regional collaboration, and policy-relevant insights for scaling PES initiatives across the HKH.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 11:00–12:30

Panel B1 | The economics of springshed management and springs restoration in the HKH

Moderator:

Sarala Khaling

Head of Resilient Economies and Landscapes, ICIMOD, Nepal

Panellists

- **Giacomo Butte**, Built Environment Consultant, Italy
- **Seema Purushothaman**, President, Indian Society for Ecological Economics (INSEE), India
- **A.K. Enamul Haque**, Professor and Director General, Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies (BIDS), Bangladesh; SANDEE Advisor
- **Subhrendu K. Pattanayak**, Oak Foundation Distinguished Professor of Environmental and Energy Policy, Duke University, USA
- **Rajesh Kumar Rai**, Professor, Institute of Forestry, Nepal

Abstract

The Hindu Kush Himalaya (HKH) region, often referred to as the ‘Third Pole’, is a vital water source for over 1.9 billion people across eight countries: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, China, India, Myanmar, Nepal, and Pakistan. Springs are the primary source of drinking and irrigation water for millions living in the mid-hill and mountain areas of this region. However, springs across the HKH are drying or showing reduced discharge due to climate change (precipitation patterns, droughts), land-use change (degradation), deforestation, and unregulated groundwater extraction. This panel on the economics of springshed management and spring restoration will focus on articulating the economic value of springs and springsheds in the HKH, assessing the costs of degradation and the benefits and returns to restoration, and examining financing mechanisms and incentives for sustaining springshed management at scale. Panellists include environmental and resource economists, a government representative, and a development partner who will draw on regional experiences and community-led models from the HKH and beyond. They will discuss tools and methodologies for the economic assessment of ecosystem services, and how economic evidence can inform water security and climate policy, support community investment, and guide the design of financial instruments and policy interventions for long-term springshed resilience.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 11:00–12:30

Panel B2 | Harnessing Big data and digital technologies for economic development in the HKH

Moderator

Birendra Bajracharya,

Interim Senior Intervention Manager

– Regional Information Service, ICIMOD, Nepal

Panellists

- **David Potter**, Head of Regional Action and Global Advocacy, ICIMOD, Nepal
- **Shanlong Lu**, Professor, International Coordinator of SDG 6, International Research Center of Big Data for Sustainable Development Goals (CBAS), Aerospace Information Research Institute, Chinese Academy of Sciences (AIRCAS), China
- **Bibhusan Bista**, Executive President, Young Innovations Pvt. Ltd., Nepal
- **Sudip Pradhan**, Senior Geospatial Application Development Specialist, ICIMOD, Nepal

Abstract

Big data and digital technologies are reshaping economic and social life in the Hindu Kush Himalaya (HKH), from how people farm and trade to how they move and access services. ICIMOD's Regional Information Service (RIS) is an intervention with the aim of influencing regional and national policy, planning and investment decisions through improved access to data, information and insight on regional climate and environmental trends. This panel session will showcase ongoing initiatives related to big data and digital platforms in sectors such as agriculture, trade, tourism, and industry. Panellists will examine their potential for inclusive, climate-resilient economic development, the risks linked to gaps in connectivity, affordability, literacy, governance, and data sovereignty, and how regional cooperation and partnerships can help scale effective digital solutions across borders in the HKH.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 11:00–12:30

Panel B3 | Landscape resource conservation for improving water availability, building climate resilience, and strengthening ecosystem services: Evidence from India

Moderator

S. Madheswaran

Professor and Head, Centre for Economic Studies and Policy Institute for Social and Economic Change, India

Panellists

- **Kaushal K Garg**, Principal Scientist- Natural Resource Management, India
- **Anantha KH**, Principal Scientist I - Natural Resource Management, International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics, Hyderabad, India

Abstract

Land degradation and natural resource depletion threaten agricultural sustainability in semi-arid regions such as Bundelkhand region, Uttar Pradesh, India. In Bundelkhand region, recurrent droughts, erratic rainfall, and poor soil fertility have caused low productivity and rural distress. Recognizing the need for a holistic solution, the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT), with support from the Government of Uttar Pradesh, initiated a comprehensive landscape restoration program covering 28,000 ha across 40 villages. Using a hydrology-based Landscape Resource Conservation approach, the program integrated natural resource mapping, local knowledge, and decentralised water and soil management through havelis, check dams, percolation tanks, farm ponds, and agroforestry models. These interventions improved groundwater levels (2-3 times), raised cropping intensity (110% to 180%), and diversified livelihoods. Tahrauli's transformation highlights that participatory, science-based NRM can enhance water security, productivity, and ecosystem resilience, offering a replicable model for dryland regions globally.

Paper abstracts

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 13:30–15:00

PARALLEL SESSION A1

Technology and sustainability in agriculture

Chair

Soumya Balasubramaniya

Senior Economist, The World Bank, Washington DC, USA

Economic incentives for artificial intelligence-based digital technologies for sustainable agriculture

Presenter

Madhu Khanna,

Distinguished Professor, Co-Director, Center for Economics of Sustainability,
University of Illinois, USA

Discussant

Soumya Balasubramaniya

Senior Economist, The World Bank, Washington DC, USA

Abstract

Rapid advances and diffusion of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies have the potential to transform agriculture globally by improving measurement, prediction and site-specific management on the farm, enabling autonomous equipment that is trained to mimic human behaviour and developing recommendation systems designed to autonomously achieve various tasks. This talk will describe the economic incentives for the adoption of applications of AI-enabled technologies in agriculture and various ways through which these technologies can address current challenges in agriculture and their risks and benefits for small and large-scale farmers.

Climate-smart agricultural innovations: Policy frameworks for adaptation, mitigation, and technology diffusion

Presenter

V. Saravanakumar

Professor, Agricultural Economics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India

Co-author(s)

D. Suresh Kumar

Professor, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India

A. Vidhyavathi

Professor, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India

Discussant

Abid Hussain

Economies Lead, ICIMOD, Nepal

Abstract

This study evaluates climate-smart agricultural practices (CSAPs), viz. System of Rice Intensification (SRI) and Direct Seeded Rice (DSR) in comparison to the conventional flooding rice farming method, focusing on economic and environmental impacts. SRI recorded the highest yield, water and nutrient-use efficiency, and higher net returns (INR 56,886.96), followed by DSR (INR 44,285.12) and conventional (INR 41,303.49). Greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions were highest in the conventional method (10,937 kg CO₂eq/ha), while DSR and SRI significantly reduced emissions and social cost of carbon by 37% and 45%, respectively. Adoption of these practices was positively influenced by education, extension services, farming experience, farm location and water access. Given the low adoption of CSAPs, intensifying agricultural extension systems through trainings and demonstrations and introducing carbon credit incentives can encourage wider uptake, especially limited irrigation conditions.

Enhancing food security through food security of farmers: a look at how to implement commercial and organic farming among smallholder farmers

Presenter

Tshotsho

Lecturer, Department of Sustainable Development, College of Natural Resources, Royal University of Bhutan, Bhutan

Discussant:

Pawan Kumar Sharma

Professor and Head of Department (Agricultural Economics), Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences & Technology of Jammu (J&K), India

Abstract

Achieving food security is a matter of significant concern for numerous governments, including those of countries where smallholder subsistence farming constitutes the prevailing agricultural system. Nevertheless, a considerable body of research neglects to address the issue of food security among farmers. This research explores the efficacy of a popular policy that utilises commercialisation and the introduction of organic farming among smallholder farmers to address food security. The study examines the policy's ability to ensure food security for farmers. The present study utilises data from the 2019 agricultural census survey in Bhutan to assess the capacity of farmers to meet their own production needs. The primary objective of the research is to examine this question from the perspective of intervention. The results of the analysis indicate that a significant proportion of subsistence farmers are unable to satisfy their own food requirements through their own production. The findings from the analyses of the covarying effects demonstrate that the implementation of commercialisation and organic farming in districts characterised by subsistence and conventional farming practices, where farmers are capable of meeting their own food requirements, has the potential to yield effective outcomes. The objective of the present study was to ascertain geographical areas suitable for the implementation of large-scale commercial and organic farming techniques, with the aim of enhancing food security at the national level.

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 13:30–15:00

PARALLEL SESSION A2

Climate policies and livelihoods

Chair

Sarala Khaling

Head of Resilient Economies and Landscapes, ICIMOD, Nepal

The public's views on climate policies in seven large Global South countries

Presenter

Thomas Sterner, Professor, Environmental Economics, University of Gothenburg, Sweden

Co-author (s)

Richard T. Carson, Professor, Environmental Economics, UC San Diego, USA

Jiajun Lu, Assistant Professor, International Business School, Zhejiang University, Haining, China

Emily A. Khossravi, College of Arts and Sciences, Harvard University, Cambridge, MA, USA

Gunnar Köhlin, Director, Environment for Development, Associate Professor, School of Business, Economics and Law, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden

Erik Sterner, Researcher, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden

Dale Whittington, Professor, Chapel Hill UNC Gillings School of Global Public Health, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, North Carolina, USA

Discussant

Ashish Tiwari, Air Lead, ICIMOD, Nepal

Abstract

While public attitudes regarding climate change have been widely explored in the global north, survey work is still limited in the global south. Here we analysed survey data (n = 8,400) from Chile, Colombia, India, Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa, and Vietnam to understand climate knowledge, trusted information sources and policy preferences. Our results indicate that scientists stand out as the most trusted information source in all countries except Vietnam, and trust in scientists correlates with increased climate knowledge. Respondents agree with the urgency of the climate change challenge, but prioritising policies to mitigate climate change substantially declines when policy trade-offs are introduced. There is broad agreement for earmarking carbon tax revenue towards health and education, renewable energy subsidies and clean technology R&D, but little support for deficit reduction or uniform rebates.

Does climate vulnerability drive public health spending? evidence from South and Southeast Asia (2000–2022)

Presenter

Mohammad Iftekharul Islam

Research Associate, South Asian Network on Economic Modeling (SANEM), Dhaka

Co-author(s)

Rassiq Aziz Kabir

Research Associate, Research and Policy Integration for Development (RAPID), Bangladesh

Numair M N Ahmmed

Research Associate, UCB Stock Brokerage Ltd, Bangladesh

Ismot Hasnine Masrur E Khuda

Graduate Student, Department of Geography and Environment, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

Discussant

Lubna Naz

Professor and Director, Center for Business and Economic Research, Institute of Business Administration Karachi, Pakistan

Abstract

Climate change affects almost all sectors of our planet. One of the most critical sectors affected is public healthcare, which, due to its important role in safeguarding human well-being, is particularly vulnerable to climate change. Given the heterogeneous nature of climate change impacts, its influence on the healthcare sector varies among countries. Thus, countries are seen to adopt distinct domestic strategies to counter this. This study utilises a panel dataset comprising 13 countries across South and Southeast Asia. Because of their geographic location and economic constraints, such countries tend to be more vulnerable to climate change. This study utilises the ND-GAIN Climate Vulnerability Index to evaluate how such vulnerability influences public spending on healthcare. The findings showcase a clear decline in public health expenditure as climate vulnerability increases. This trend is likely due to the economic limitations of many countries in the region, as most still remain in the developing and underdeveloped stage. These nations often lack the economic resilience to absorb the financial shocks caused by extreme climate events. As a result, they tend to reduce investment in sectors such as healthcare during times of environmental stress.

Climate risk and tribal livelihoods in Central India: Assessment of institutional welfare schemes and tribal resilience

Presenter

Mohanasundari Thangavel

Associate Professor, Indian Institute of Technology Indore, Madhya Pradesh, India

Co-author(s)

Gaurav Banaula

Research Assistant, Indian Institute of Technology Indore, Madhya Pradesh, India

Amit Kumar

Research Scholar, Indian Institute of Technology Indore, Madhya Pradesh, India

Discussant

Sarala Khaling

Head of Resilient Economies and Landscapes, ICIMOD, Nepal

Abstract

This study examines the climate vulnerability of tribal households in Dhar district, Madhya Pradesh, particularly focusing on gender disparities. Using the IPCC framework, it calculates a Livelihood Vulnerability Index (LVI) based on exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity. Findings show that female-headed households face higher exposure (0.515 vs. 0.454 for males) and sensitivity (0.366 vs. 0.350), with lower adaptive capacity (0.340 vs. 0.410) when compared with their counterparts, invariably in all the categories. Key factors include limited landholdings, poor housing, and restricted access to education and resources for females. Farming enhances resilience, but sole reliance on agriculture leaves female households vulnerable to crop losses and financial instability due to climate change. The study highlights the need for targeted policies to address these gaps and strengthen resilience among marginalized groups and calls for approaches that prioritize equitable resource distribution, inclusive decision-making, and adaptive strategies to mitigate climate-induced vulnerabilities which contributes to SDG 5 (Gender Equality), Goal 10 (Reduced Inequalities), and Goal 13 Climate Action).

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 13:30–15:00

PARALLEL SESSION A3 |

Environmental sustainability: Methods and issues

Chair

A.K. Enamul Haque

Director General, Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies (BIDS), Bangladesh

Methodological issues in empirical research in environmental and development economics

Presenter

Jean Marie Baland

Professor, Department of Economics, University of Namur, Belgium

Discussant

A.K. Enamul Haque

Director General, Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies (BIDS), Bangladesh

Abstract

In these notes, I discuss some of the difficulties faced by young researchers when starting an empirical project in environmental and development economics. I focus in particular on the need to understand the available data correctly, and on the need for a clear conceptual approach to measure the variables as well as establish causal relations between them.

Trodding through environmental and sustainability issues since the 1990s: a reflection

Presenter

Sajjad Zohir

Executive Director, Economic Research Group (ERG), Dhaka, Bangladesh

Discussant

Heman Das Lohano

Visiting Professor, Department of Applied Economics, University of Minnesota, USA

Abstract

My journey with SANDEE began in 1999 when Priya, an alien to me till then, walked into my office at BIDS. The journey since then has taken me through riddles, many of which remain unresolved to this date. This brief is an attempt to reflect on that journey over the last 30 years – as a researcher, a SANDEE activist during its infancy, and as a citizen in Bangladesh. The presentation highlights a few of those riddles.

- Purpose of environmental accounting – the fear of economic reasoning in making choices buried under monitoring interests with audits and accounts.
- Rise of sea/ocean level and the emergence of landmass in the estuary – are we undermining land subsidence, particularly those arising from the extraction of underground resources?
- Ever-growing urban air quality with little or no action to reduce vehicular pollution – are we undermining the importance of the latter?
- ‘Competition’ to protect one’s share in (or grab more from) the limited supply of water from the local authority (WASA in Bangladesh), total private expenditure on pumps increases, without adding a net increase in total water received. Yet, we find little effort to find alternatives under ‘collectives’ for fear of the ‘tragedy of the commons!
- Searching for a solution in urban sewerage – unknown trade-offs between organic and inorganic fertiliser and the race to higher land productivity.
- Internalizing negative externalities – where does that practice begin? And where do we draw the lines on hygiene?

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 13:30–15:00

PARALLEL SESSION A4 |

Environmental health

Chair

Bhim Adhikari

Senior Program Specialist,
International Development Research Centre (IDRC), Canada

A nature-based solution? Evaluating a health care provider nature exercise prescription using a pilot randomized controlled trial (RCT) data from rural Oregon, USA

Presenter

Randall Bluffstone,

Professor of Economics and Director, Institute for Economics and the Environment, Portland State University, USA

Co-author(s)

Ma Chan, Student, Portland State University, USA

Cort Cox, Research Project Coordinator, Oregon Health & Science University, Portland, USA

Melinda M. Davis, Professor, School of Medicine, Oregon Health & Science University, Portland, USA

Caitlin Dickinson, Director, Community Engaged Research, Oregon Health & Science University, Portland, USA

Sahan T. M. Dissanayake, Associate Professor, Department of Economics, Portland State University, Portland, USA

Anushka Karel

Jeffrey D. Kline, Research Forester, USDA Forest Service, Pacific Northwest Research Station, Corvallis, USA

Citlactli Carrera López, Department of Economics, Portland State University, Portland, USA

Himani Ojha, ISS Graduate Student Fellow, Department of Economics, Portland State University, Portland, USA

Sterling Stokes, MPH, Environmental Systems & Human Health, School of Medicine, Oregon Health & Science University, Portland, USA

Saurabh S. Thosar, Associate Professor, Oregon Health & Science University, Portland, USA

Srilakshmi Vedantam, Graduate student, Portland State University, Portland, USA

Discussant

Pallab Mozumder, Department of Economics, Department of Earth and Environment, Florida International University, USA

Abstract

Evidence appears to be building that direct exposure to natural landscapes characterised by significant green cover, such as forests, can help to reduce chronic health conditions such as obesity, stress, hypertension, chronic cardiovascular conditions, depression, anxiety, cancer, and diabetes. One way to encourage greater exposure to nature may be through the use of nature prescriptions, whereby clinicians formally recommend (or prescribe) time in nature to their patients. This paper estimates the effects of health care provider-prescribed exercise in forests on daily, self-reported health, sleep and exercise outcomes among adults with one or more chronic health conditions and ongoing recommendations to increase exercise. It presents results from a small-sample pilot randomised control trial conducted in two clinics in rural Oregon, USA.

Society's willingness to pay for less health risks by pesticide use: A case study

Presenter

Prema A, Professor and Head, Dept. of Agricultural Economics, Kerala Agricultural University, India

Co-author(s)

S Vaishnavi, PG Scholar, Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Vellanikkara, India

C D Neetha Rose, Assistant Professor (Agricultural Economics), Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Pattambi, Palakkad, India

Discussant

Bhim Adhikari, Senior Program Specialist, International Development Research Centre (IDRC), Canada

Abstract

Integrated pest management represents a comprehensive and sustainable approach to managing pests in agricultural systems. This study enumerates the willingness of consumers to pay for pesticide residue-free rice produced by adopting Integrated pest management (IPM). A logistic regression framework was used to assess the consumer's choice to pay. The majority of the consumers expressed their WTP for reducing the risk associated with pesticide use. The average WTP for rice produced through IPM technology was Rs.6.92 per kg at the retail level. A binary logistic regression was used to analyse the relationship between consumers' willingness to pay to reduce the risk associated with pesticide use and different independent variables. The WTP of consumers was influenced by their age, annual income, perceived benefits from IPM, total monthly expenditure and monthly consumption. While monthly expenditure exerted a negative influence, age, annual income, perceived benefits and monthly consumption of consumers positively influenced the WTP to reduce the risk.

Can female leaders promote better health behaviour? Learning from a sanitation-and-hygiene communication experiment in rural Bangladesh

Presenter

Atonu Rabbani,

Professor, Department of Economics, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

Discussant

Bishal Bharadwaj

Research Associate, Global Research Initiative, University of Calgary, Canada

Abstract

In this study, we look at an important environmental health issue of access to quality sanitation and hygiene practices and how local women leaders can possibly mitigate the problem through information and education campaign and promotion. Pathogens of faecal origins (coliforms and other bacteria in addition to helminthes) still pose an important public health hazard for the poor households in Bangladesh and elsewhere, which imposes a significant disease and mortality burden. We devise an experiment where we exogenously vary the leadership capacity of the women leaders and their involvement in the sanitation and hygiene campaigns. We find that, in the treatment areas, the households report higher interaction with the local women leaders and also with the community women group members compared to the control areas. However, we do not find that the households reduced the practice of open defecation (which was already very low before the interventions) and also did not result in any higher level of latrine construction. We further look at objective hand hygiene outcomes as measured by bacteriological counts in the hands of the very young children and their primary female caregivers. We find that interactions with the local women leaders have positive impacts on hand hygiene outcomes as suggested by reduction in microbial counts of total coliforms, faecal coliforms and *E. coli* in the hand samples of the young children but not for the mothers. Very importantly, we also find that promotion activities may have selection on the possible gains and the local leaders may have deliberately targeted households for which promotion can have higher positive effects. We conclude that leadership capacity can be effective in improving sanitation and hygiene outcomes that are mainly behavioural in nature and does not involve substantial financial investment.

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 13:30–15:00

PARALLEL SESSION A5

Forest and Livelihoods

Chair

Lucy Emerton

Director, Conservation Economics and Finance,
Environment Management Group, Sri Lanka

Effects of organised guarding on mortality from human-elephant conflict in Northeast India

Presenter

E. Somanathan

Professor, Economics and Planning Unit, Indian Statistical Institute, India

Discussant

Lucy Emerton, Director, Conservation Economics and Finance, Environment Management Group, Sri Lanka

Abstract

Human-elephant conflict (HEC) frequently results in human and elephant mortality, posing major social justice and conservation concerns across Asia and Africa. While a variety of interventions have been introduced to mitigate HEC, rigorous evaluations of how they affect mortality are practically absent. Using a twenty-year data set from Sonitpur district in Assam, India, we assess whether organised guarding and short-distance drives – which are used to manage HEC in several countries globally – lead to a reduction in human and elephant mortality from conflict as intended. Controlling for changes in land use and economic development, spillover effects, and non-random selection of villages for intervention, we are unable to conclude whether or not organised guarding provides any protection against human death due to HEC. Contrary to expectations, the intervention is associated with an approximately 2.0-2.9 times increase in elephant mortality, with evidence suggesting elephants may be more likely to suffer an accidental death in villages where organised guarding occurs. Our study highlights the indispensability of rigorous evaluations for finding win-win solutions to human-wildlife conflict.

Assessing the livelihood Impacts of non-government organisation-led forest restoration in village common forests: A case study

Presenter

Md. Shafiqul Bari

Vice-Chancellor, EXIM Bank Agricultural University Bangladesh, Bangladesh

Discussant

Abul Kalam Azad

Senior Intervention Manager- Livelihoods and Enterprises, ICIMOD, Nepal

Abstract

Village Common Forests (VCFs) in Bangladesh's Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT) are crucial for the livelihoods of local ethnic communities, offering essential resources and protecting vital watersheds. However, deforestation and unsustainable practices threaten the health of VCFs and the communities that depend on them, prompting interventions by Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and other stakeholders to restore forests and support alternative livelihoods. Yet, the effectiveness of these interventions requires further investigation. Therefore, this study critically evaluates the role of NGOs in VCF practice and livelihood enhancement in VCFs in the CHT, Bangladesh. The Sustainable Livelihood Approach and Propensity Score Matching were used in 30 VCFs, half with NGO involvement and half without NGO involvement, to assess the impact of NGOs. The findings reveal that households in VCFs managed by NGOs had higher incomes, lower spending, and higher education levels. Factors such as age, market proximity, education, occupation, and land size influenced NGO forest restoration activities. According to nearest neighbour and kernel matching methods, households involved in NGO-led VCF restoration had 1.38- and 1.26-times higher livelihood status, respectively. However, VCF communities face challenges such as land rights disputes, limited training, communication, and political unrest in forest restoration efforts. These findings advocate for government-NGO engagement in biodiversity and sustainability-focused forest restoration programs.

Government support for tree-growing by farmers: Evidence from India's agroforestry programs

Presenter

Chandan Singha

Associate Professor, Hindu College, University of Delhi, India

Discussant

Prabath Nishantha Edirisinghe

Retired Conservator General of Forests, Department of Forest Conservation, Sri Lanka

Abstract

Agroforestry is a promising natural climate solution that can enhance and diversify farm incomes. This study evaluates the effectiveness of government-supported agroforestry programs in India by integrating survey data from 870 farm households across 59 villages with geospatial information on factors affecting tree growing. Results show that government support led to a 19% increase in farmer involvement in commercial tree cultivation. Moreover, participation significantly increased the number of commercial trees planted by farmers, with increases of 157% in total trees, 96% in trees per acre, and 100% in the proportion of timber trees. Program participation, not simply program knowledge, was crucial: farmers who knew of but did not participate in government-supported programs did not expand their tree-growing activities. For those not exposed to government programs, factors such as climate (precipitation and temperature), spatial variation, including jurisdictional differences, and household characteristics (land size) were important predictors of tree cultivation. Our findings highlight the efficacy and need for continued public investments in agroforestry.

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 15:30–17:00

PARALLEL SESSION B1

Forest conservation and management

Chair

Jeffrey Vincent

Clarence F Korstian Professor of Forest Economics and Management,
Nicholas School of the Environment, Duke University, USA

Community forest management: Unveiling the success story of Nepal

Presenter

François Libois, Professor, Research Fellow and Professor, Paris School of Economics & INRAe, France

Co-author(s)

Jean-Marie Baland Professor, University of Namur, Belgium

Nicolas Delbart, Professor, Université Paris-Cité, France

Subhrendu K. Pattanayak, Oak Foundation Distinguished Professor of Environmental and Energy Policy, Duke University, USA

Discussant

Jeffrey Vincent, Clarence F Korstian Professor of Forest Economics and Management, Nicholas School of the Environment, Duke University, USA

Abstract

Nepal has implemented one of the most ambitious and comprehensive programs of forest management decentralisation in the world since 1993. The program has been widely recognised as a successful example of participatory natural resource management. We first quantify the net increase in tree vegetation resulting from the program and how this change evolved over time in the Hills and Mountains of Nepal. We then assess the relative importance of tree leaf density relative to forested areas in contributing to these changes. We finally discuss some of the mechanisms driving forest restoration, emphasising the role community forestry also played in reducing immediate demand pressures by altering energy choices.

Dynamics of Community Forest User Group (CFUG) creation and spillover effects in Nepal's community forestry

Presenter

Marine Gueben, PhD candidate, University of Namur, Belgium

Co-author(s)

J-M Baland, Professor, University of Namur, Belgium

N. Delbart, Professor, Université Paris-Cité, France

F. Libois, Professor, Research Fellow and Professor, Paris School of Economics & INRAe, France

Discussant

Rajesh Kumar Rai, Professor, School of Forestry and Natural Resource Management, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Abstract

This project analyses how participatory forest governance shapes spatial and social inequalities by studying the diffusion and externalities of Nepal's Community Forest User Groups (CFUGs). Although community forestry is widely presented as an inclusive model of natural-resource management, empirical evidence shows that it often reflects pre-existing hierarchies of caste, wealth, and geographic accessibility. Yet the mechanisms through which these inequalities emerge and evolve across space remain insufficiently understood. Using an original georeferenced dataset of 2,700 CFUGs merged with forest inventories, population censuses, and remote-sensing indicators (2000–2010), the project reconstructs forty years of CFUG formation and evaluates its consequences. The analysis focuses on three dimensions. First, it measures ecological spillovers by comparing forest conditions inside and around CFUG boundaries, testing whether regulated access improves local forest quality or displaces extraction to neighbouring areas. Second, it identifies institutional spillovers by examining whether the presence of nearby CFUGs increases the probability and speed of adoption in adjacent communities, and how geography and demographics condition this diffusion. Third, it characterises exclusion by assessing which groups – socially and spatially – did not gain access to CFUGs and whether early adopters secured larger or higher-quality forests. By integrating spatial data, ecological indicators, and social composition, the project provides new evidence on the territorial inequalities embedded in participatory governance and their long-term implications for resource access.

What is a good mountain forest? and for whom?

Presenter

Dil Bahadur Khatri, Executive Director and Senior Researcher, Southasia Institute of Advanced Studies (SIAS), Kathmandu, Nepal

Discussant

Sony Baral, Assistant Dean, Institute of Forestry, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Abstract

The governing of forests in Global South countries, guided by modern forestry and conservation sciences, focused on creating boundaries and reducing human disturbances. The policies, such as community forestry and biodiversity conservation, implemented in the South Asian Mountains, driven by degradation narratives, viewed local communities as the main culprits of forest and biodiversity loss. The governmental interventions overlooked the fact that such forest landscapes were co-created through entangled relations between nature and humans. The official claims of successful forest policy outcomes contradict local narratives of what such forests have become. The regrown forests over the past decades have failed to meet local needs, and increasing bureaucratic and institutional rules and discretionary practices have alienated local communities from forest benefits. Studies revealed that governmental planning resulted in a fracturing of the multiple layers of relations between nature and humans, generating uncertainties, i.e. alienating forest uses, growing human wildlife conflicts and declining water sources. In contrast, the emerging narrative in Europe suggests that human and non-human disturbances may not be necessarily harmful for biodiversity and ecological integrity. Emerging scholarship provides alternative perspectives to the mainstream forestry and conservation sciences and suggests we view forests as complex systems and take account of complex interaction between humans and nature, implying that forests cannot so easily be managed by plans and policies, based on prescriptive thinking. We argue that forests should be seen from the perspective of people living next to forests and their everyday interaction, which Rosa (2020) defined as resonance. Based on the critical reflection of the past interventions and outcomes of governing forests in South Asian mountains, we suggest rethinking the way we view what the 'good forest' is and how to achieve it.

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 15:30–17:00

PARALLEL SESSION B2

Environmental valuation

Chair

Ram Chandra Bhattarai

Professor (Retd.), Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Valuing the complementarity under integrated farming systems– the case of Pokkali

Presenter

Indira Devi, Professor, Kerala Agricultural University, India

Co-author(s)

Sumithra S, PhD student, Kerala Agricultural University, India

Discussant

Ram Chandra Bhattarai, Professor (Retd.), Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Abstract

Integrated Farming Systems (IFS) that combine rice cultivation with aquatic species such as fish and tiger prawn are central to the ecological and agronomic resilience of the Pokkali agroecosystem in coastal Kerala, India. While the soil-enriching and sustainability benefits of rice–fish and rice–prawn rotations are well acknowledged, the economic value arising from such ecological improvements remains under-quantified. This study estimates the complementarity value of IFS by analysing how the Soil Quality Index (SQI) influences rice yield. A two-year field assessment covering 100 farms was undertaken across Pokkali tracts affected by salinity and tidal submergence. SQI was derived through Principal Component Analysis of soil parameters, and the Relative Management Index (RMI) captured adherence to recommended practices. A Cobb–Douglas production function demonstrated strong model performance ($R^2=0.6287$), with variety, SQI, and RMI all showing positive and significant impacts on yield. A 1% increase in SQI or RMI enhanced yields by nearly 0.25%, while improved varieties increased productivity by 29.14%. Transition from monoculture to IFS boosts SQI by 41.6%, translating to ecosystem service benefits worth ₹6987/ha. The findings highlight soil quality, management, and varietal choice as mutually reinforcing determinants of productivity in Pokkali ecosystems, underscoring the need for policy incentives—such as soil monitoring support and PES frameworks—to internalise these ecological externalities.

Cleaner lakes at a price: Farmers' willingness to accept compensation for reducing chemical inputs in Myanmar's floating agriculture

Presenter

Yarzar Hein, Professor and Head of Department, Advanced Center for Agricultural Research and Education, Myanmar

Co-author(s)

Nang Ei Mon The, Department of Agricultural Economics, Yezin Agricultural University, Yezin, Nay Pyi Taw, Myanmar

Nyo Mar Htwe, Associate Professor, Advanced Center for Agricultural Research and Education, YAU, Nay Pyi Taw, Myanmar

Discussant

Kavita Sardana, Visiting Faculty of Economics, Ashoka University, India

Abstract

Floating agriculture in Myanmar's Inle Lake represents an essential source of livelihood, but affects the lake through nutrient enrichment, chemical loading, and degradation. Reducing the use of chemicals and the level of farming are increasingly recognised as necessary for lake restoration. Still, the financial motives driving farmers to reduce farming in this way are unclear. In this analysis, farmers' willingness to accept compensation regarding the reduction in floating farm area, the use of chemical fertiliser, and pesticides was estimated.

The discrete choice experiment was incorporated into a household survey of 260 floating farming households. In the discrete choice experiment, the pivoted attribute design was applied, with attribute levels consisting of proportionate reductions (20-40% for land area, 30-50% for fertiliser and pesticides) from the farm-level baseline. An optimal fractional factorial design yielded six efficient choice sets (D-efficiency = 93.7%). To alleviate respondent burden, householders responded to two randomly allocated choice sets, creating a RIBD design.

Mixed logit estimates were employed to derive marginal WTA amounts. The results show that the level of compensation required to reduce the use of fertiliser, pesticides, and cultivated land is the highest. For example, the compensation amount necessary due to the reduction in the use of fertiliser by 20% can be estimated at around US\$ 60 per 100 ha per year. Environmental awareness, household endowment, and market orientation variables are significant factors affecting the level of compensation.

Using policy analysis, the model predicts that a slight increase in compensation (e.g., USD 100 per 100 lan) can significantly encourage volunteers to participate in chemical reduction programs. Remarkably, these results underline the viability of incentive-oriented agri-environmental projects (possibly interacting with eco-labelling, sustainable tourism, or lake protection projects) in reducing the use of chemicals while keeping farming livelihoods sustainable. By offering these benefits, such projects can contribute positively towards lake restoration.

Consumers' preference and willingness to pay for Nepalese large cardamom in the global market

Presenter

Rishi Ram Kattel, Professor, Agriculture and Forestry University (AFU), Nepal

Discussant

Rajan Parajuli, Associate Professor, North Carolina State University, USA

Abstract

This paper examines the consumers' preference and willingness to pay (WTP) for Nepalese large cardamom in the global market. A total of 255 respondents were surveyed using a structured questionnaire in the KoBo Toolbox online survey during 2020. The Logit model was used for assessing factors determining consumers' WTP, and WTP regression was used to assess the monetary value of the additional WTP price premium. The average age of the respondents was 29.21 years, and 16.70 years of schooling. The average household size was 4.87 members. Two-thirds of respondents were male, and 39% respondents' occupations were service. About 92% respondents belonged to Asia, whereas 38% from urban city origins. One-fourth of respondents had USD 5000 or above annual income. Consumers were willing to pay a price premium of 34.56% for Nepalese large cardamom, while about 33% additional WTP for organically certified once. About 40% respondents expressed their willingness to pay for Nepalese large cardamom, whereas 65% expressed their additional WTP for organic certified. The average price paid for large cardamom was USD 19.6 per kg, whereas the WTP additional amount for Nepalese large cardamom was USD 6.92 per kg and USD 6.6 per kg additional for organic certified ones. Major determining factors on WTP of Nepalese large cardamom were preference based on colour, size, household expenditure and knowledge. Additional WTP of Nepalese large cardamom price premium were determined by preference based on colour, size and part of cardamom used. The results can significantly contribute to improving value added practices of Nepalese large cardamom based on consumers' preferences.

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 15:30–17:00

PARALLEL SESSION B3

Environmental Governance

Chair

Bishwa Nath Tiwari, Professor of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Valuing ecosystem assets for ecosystem accounting in the Gunbower-Koondrook-Perricoota (GKP) forest icon site in Australia

Presenter

Ram Pandit, Associate Professor, The University of Western Australia, Australia

Co-author(s)

Michael P. Burton, Associate Professor, The University of Western Australia, Australia

Kerstin K. Zander, Professor of Environmental Economics, Charles Darwin University, Australia

Stephen T. Garnett, Professor of Conservation and Sustainability, Charles Darwin University, Australia

David J. Pannell, Professor, The University of Western Australia, Australia

Discussant

Bishwa Nath Tiwari, Professor of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Abstract

Ecosystem Accounting (EA) involves tracking the extent, condition, and services provided by ecosystems and linking them to the economy under the international standard developed by the United Nations – System of Environmental-Economic Accounting. Ecosystem assets (species, ecosystems and ecological communities) provide use and non-use benefits to society. A key challenge is how to value non-market benefits that arise from these assets. This study aims to contribute to this challenge by estimating the marginal willingness to pay for key ecosystem assets in the Gunbower-Koondrook-Perricoota (GKP) Forest Icon Site in the Murray-Darling Basin of Australia, as a necessary precursor to identifying an exchange price from which to derive exchange values. A discrete choice experiment with three types of ecosystem assets as attributes was designed and implemented among the Australian public in 2021. The ecosystem asset attributes were six threatened species (Australian bittern, Painted honeyeater, Superb parrot, Koala, Green-comb spider-orchid, Winged pepper-cress), three ecosystem types (River-swamp wallaby grass, River red gum, Black box) and two species groups or ecological communities (water birds and vascular plants). The collected data was analysed using a mixed-logit model. Findings suggest that the estimated marginal willingness-to-pay (WTP) for improvement in status (population or habitat condition index) of ecosystem assets varies from AUD14.60 per year per household for 20 years for water birds to AU\$1.32 for Green-comb spider-orchid.

Assessing tourism governance and ecological integration in mountain regions: Insights from Gilgit-Baltistan

Presenter

Amjad Ali, Assistant Professor, Department of Development Studies, Karakoram International University, Pakistan

Discussant

Muhammad Rafiq, Member (Climate Finance), Pakistan Climate Change Authority, Pakistan

Abstract

Tourism in Gilgit-Baltistan is rapidly expanding, raising urgent concerns about how natural capital and ecological values are integrated into governance systems. This study examines the extent to which tourism planning and institutional arrangements in the region incorporate ecological considerations. Using a political ecology lens and institutional analysis, the research reviews policy documents, conducts semi-structured interviews with officials and stakeholders, and applies discourse analysis to understand how nature, development, and tourism are framed across governance levels. Findings reveal that tourism governance remains largely sectoral, reactive, and focused on short-term growth. Ecological data, ecosystem-service values, and environmental impact assessments are rarely embedded in decision-making processes, resulting in planning blind spots. Despite widespread recognition of issues such as land-use change, waste accumulation, and biodiversity loss, institutional capacity, policy tools, and inter-agency coordination remain weak. Ecological values are often treated instrumentally – mainly as scenic resources for tourism – rather than as integral components of sustainability. The absence of localised ecosystem indicators further limits evidence-based planning. Nonetheless, emerging NGO partnerships and rising community interest in sustainable tourism present opportunities for reform. The study highlights the need for cross-sectoral governance models that incorporate Natural Capital Accounting and long-term ecological sustainability in tourism policy for mountain regions like Gilgit-Baltistan.

Beyond access: Institutional dynamics and farmer preferences in groundwater markets in semi-critical regions of India

Presenter

Akshi Bajaj, Assistant Professor School of Business, UPES, India

Discussant

Eshita Gupta, Senior Economist, KPMG, India

Abstract

This study investigates farmers' perceptions and preferences regarding institutional transitions in groundwater governance in the semi-critical regions of Western Uttar Pradesh, India. Groundwater markets in India, though informal, have evolved as crucial mechanisms for irrigation access, especially for marginal and small farmers. However, these markets operate in the absence of regulation, contributing to unsustainable extraction and inequitable access. Based on a primary survey of 300 farm households, the study applies a multi-method framework comprising descriptive statistics, multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA), interaction term analysis, and latent class modeling (LCM). The empirical analysis reveals that support for regulatory interventions such as water metering, user rights, and volumetric pricing is significantly higher among buyers and socially marginalised groups. In contrast, sellers and large farmers exhibit a stronger preference for maintaining informal market arrangements. Latent class analysis identifies three distinct groups: Reform-Ready Conservationists, Status-Quo Stakeholders, and Skeptical Moderates. These behavioural segments reflect the heterogeneity in farmer preferences and underline the importance of designing governance reforms that are tailored to local socio-economic realities. Interaction term analysis further highlights how landholding size and market roles intersect to shape support for formalisation. The study recommends a phased and incentive-compatible approach to reform, including metering technologies, defined user rights, progressive pricing, and decentralised awareness programs. By aligning economic rationality with institutional feasibility, the paper contributes to the discourse on sustainable, inclusive, and climate-resilient groundwater management in India's agrarian landscape.

Can polycentric and adaptive approaches strengthen environmental governance in the Maldives?

Presenter

Mohamed Shumais, The Maldives National University, Maldives

Discussant

Niraj Prakash Joshi, Associate Professor, The IDEC Institute Hiroshima University, Japan

Abstract

Environmental governance in the Maldives is shaped by dispersed geography, overlapping institutional responsibilities and uneven operational capacity. Although environmental protection is articulated as a national priority, implementation remains fragmented across multiple institutions. This study examines how these arrangements function across space, drawing on protected area management plans and interviews with national agencies, councils, police, and park managers. The findings show that monitoring, enforcement, and information flow are constrained not by isolated operational gaps but by structural features of the governance system. The analysis integrates insights from polycentric governance, commons-based stewardship, and Atoll Economics, introduced in this paper. Polycentric perspectives help explain why coordination weakens when responsibilities are widely distributed but supporting mechanisms are limited. Commons approaches highlight how community interpretations shape the legitimacy of environmental rules. Atoll Economics draws attention to ecological and socioeconomic processes that operate across atoll basins, often exceeding the scale of island-level administrative units. Together, these perspectives provide an integrated understanding of why fragmentation persists. The study outlines institutional directions for further exploration, including a dedicated nature park management service, atoll-level coordination units and stronger scientific monitoring. This approach helps to better align governance structures with the spatial realities of a country composed of multiple atolls.

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 15:30–17:00

PARALLEL SESSION B4

Energy transition

Chair

Shreekant Gupta, Professor, Delhi School of Economics, India

Power sector for the developing Asian Regions by 2050: Modelling the strategic vision

Presenter

Joyashree Roy, Distinguished Professor, Asian Institute of Technology (AIT), Thailand

Discussant

Shreekant Gupta, Professor, Delhi School of Economics, India

Abstract

The biggest challenge of this century for the less developed countries in Asia is how to innovatively expand the sustainable energy system. How can the advantage of low share in historical emissions, relatively low per capita emissions, and the emerging electrification trend be leveraged by the region? While planning for energy system expansion, integration of end-use demand side mitigation options provides multiple human wellbeing and sustainable growth benefits, helps in democratising business through granular technology choice within end-use sectors, and creates new employment opportunities. Optimising the energy supply sector, which is going to be dominated by wide-scale electrification, is an essential step, with supply-side clean energy options providing a scope for faster access to affordable clean energy. It delivers multiple co-benefits along dimensions of human wellbeing and sustainable development. Demand side mitigation options unleash business opportunity through expansion of digitalisation, integration of advanced technology in modernising distribution network, market expansion for energy efficient appliances, regional power-trade while increasing penetration of renewable energy and demand side flexibility into the system. Model-based power sector planning for emerging Asian countries helps identify new economic opportunities and wider societal benefits while decarbonising the sector. We developed a customised open-source national-scale PyPSA model for a power sector expansion plan for Bangladesh and Thailand. The open source IDEEA model developed for selected states of India for power sector planning shows how strategically alternative pathways to the mid-century zero carbon goal can be planned. National scale optimisation models and the use of national data sources clearly show that even with carbon constraints, new investment opportunities in new sectors exist. They can deliver acceptable, affordable, and accessible energy service provision systems. Such scientific evidence building and communication for deliberation on a possible new development trajectory among various social actors is necessary to create a socio-political mobilisation process for change.

Can reliable electricity supply drive induction cooktop adoption? Evidence from a randomised experiment in Kathmandu Valley

Presenter:

Naveen Adhikari, Assistant Professor, Central Department of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Discussant:

Hari Katuwal, Associate Professor, Tarleton State University, USA

Abstract

An unreliable electricity supply poses a substantial barrier for urban households in Nepal, considering the transition to induction cooktops from widely used Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) based stoves. Frequent power outages, irregular supply, and voltage instability discourage the use of these efficient and environmentally friendly appliances. To examine the role of electricity reliability and information framing in influencing usage, we conducted a randomised controlled trial involving 875 urban residents from 16 municipalities in the Kathmandu Valley. The study addressed two questions: (i) whether improved electricity reliability increases the use of induction cooktops, and (ii) which type of informational message is more effective in encouraging such use. Participants were randomly assigned to one control group and two treatment groups. The control group received basic cost comparisons between induction cooktops and LPG stoves. Treatment Group 1 was provided with information on general improvements in electricity supply, while Treatment Group 2 received the same message framed with a specific assurance of guaranteed 24-hour electricity. Baseline household characteristics were balanced across groups. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimates indicate that households in Treatment Group 2 allocated significantly more cooking time to induction cooktops, whereas no statistically significant effect was observed for Treatment Group 1. In particular, households in Treatment Group 2 reported an average of 12 additional minutes of daily induction cooktop use relative to the control group when assured of uninterrupted electricity supply. These results suggest that unreliable electricity is an obstacle to the use of induction cooktops and highlight the effectiveness of clear and credible information from electricity providers. We conclude that sustained improvements in electricity distribution infrastructure, combined with targeted nudges, are essential to accelerating the adoption of clean cooking technologies in urban Nepal.

Prepayment and electricity usage in temperature extremes: Implications for energy poverty and climate justice

Presenter

Debasish Kumar Das, Lecturer in Economics, The University of New South Wales (UNSW), Canberra, Australia

Co-author(s)

Zhenxuan Wang, Assistant Professor, North Carolina State University, USA

Discussant

Jin Yana, Assistant Professor, Peking University, China

Abstract

Prepayment systems, though benefiting utilities' revenue recovery, could impose additional burdens on disadvantaged households. This paper provides novel evidence on how prepaid metering affects households' electricity-temperature relationship. Leveraging a novel dataset on 150,000 customers' billing records in Bangladesh, we find that households' electricity consumption becomes remarkably less responsive to temperature after they are enrolled in prepayment systems. Larger effects are documented among households with lower wealth or education levels. Prepaid households tend to engage in mental accounting on their electricity consumption, especially during hot seasons. Our results imply that prepaid metering might have an unintended impact on energy poverty and climate justice.

Response to Incentives to conserve electricity and household behavior: Evidence from field experiment

Presenter

Ngawang Dendup, Consultant (Economist), Asian Development Bank Institute (ADBI)

Co-author(s)

Dil Rahut, Vice Chair of Research and Senior Research Economist, Asian Development Bank Institute, Tokyo, Japan

Magnus Soderberg, Professor, Griffith University, Australia

Karma Yoezer, Lecturer, Royal University of Bhutan, Bhutan

Discussant

Santosh Adhikari, Assistant Professor and Program Coordinator, Kathmandu University, Nepal

Abstract

Electricity access is becoming increasingly universal in developing countries, raising important questions about the impact of electricity conservation programs on household welfare and the intensive margin of electricity use. In this study, we investigate whether conservation programs – particularly those that reduce electricity consumption – negatively affect household outcomes. We also estimate the marginal effect of an additional unit of electricity consumption on these outcomes. To address the endogeneity of electricity use, we exploit exogenous variation generated through the random assignment of monetary incentives to conserve electricity. Our findings suggest that electricity conservation programs do not significantly affect key household outcomes. We further develop a simple economic model to conduct counterfactual analysis, which indicates that marginal increases in electricity prices are unlikely to induce households to substitute away from electricity toward traditional fuels in the developing country context.

DAY 02

Saturday, 13 December 2025 | 15:30–17:00

PARALLEL SESSION B5

Climate change and agriculture

Chair

Sudamini Das, Professor in Economics, Institute of Economic Growth, Delhi, India

Do institutions, incentives, and information enhance adoption of climate-smart agriculture practices? Empirical evidence from India

Presenter

Chandrasekhar Bahinipati, Head, Associate Professor, Indian Institute of Technology Tirupati, India

Co-author(s)

P.K. Viswanathan, Professor, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, India

Aparajay Kumar Singh, Assistant Professor, St. Xavier's University, India

Discussant

Mohammed Ziaul Haider, Professor, Economics Discipline, Khulna University, Bangladesh

Abstract

Over the years, numerous studies have identified factors influencing farmers' adaptive behaviour in India; however, there is a dearth of studies with respect to determinants like institutions, incentives, and information. This study, therefore, aims to fill this gap by assessing the role of these factors in driving climate-smart agriculture practices. In total, 1,274 farmers were surveyed from the 11 disaster-prone districts of four coastal states, namely, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Kerala, and Maharashtra. From the survey, it is observed that farmers are adopting seven non-mutually exclusive options, and thus, a multivariate probit model is employed. Our findings are: (i) more than 90% of the farmers adopt at least one option, and the most preferred measures are shifting of the crops, disaster-resilient crops, water management, and soil management options; (ii) in line with previous studies, the major determinants under household characteristics are livelihood diversification, and assets and amenities; (iii) access to soil health card is observed as the crucial factor for uptake of various options; (iv) none of the variables under institutions and incentives, and information, except for access to agro-met advisory services, are viewed as a major cause for adoption of all climate-smart agriculture options, but the mixed causal association is noticed for some of the measures. Concerning policy implications, this study advocates diversification of income sources, scaling up programs related to soil health card and agro-met advisory services, and restructuring existing institutions, developmental interventions, incentive mechanisms, and communication channels. It is essential since the support of policies and institutions are needed for the diffusion of agricultural innovations.

Crop diversification in a flood-affected landscape: Evidence from the Morigaon District of Assam, India

Presenter

Monjit Borthakur, Assistant Professor, Department of Geography, Cotton University, India

Co-author(s)

Ananya Saikia, Research Scholar, Cotton University, India

Discussant

Kishor Goswami, Professor of Economics, IIT Kharagpur, India

Abstract

Cropping diversification under natural hazards like floods has a significant influence on the livelihoods of farm households. Using empirical evidence from 218 farm households in eight villages of the Morigaon district of Assam, India, we examine the factors that determine the decision of crop cultivation. Our findings show that the size and type of the farmland, mechanisation, irrigation, and marketability influence crop choice. Rural households having nonfarm income also show a negative response to crop diversification. Farmers have modified their cropping patterns and agricultural cycle as a response to floods. It is important to focus on multiple stressors for crop diversification in the rural landscape of Assam. We conclude that interventions to improve non-farm-based livelihoods, along with institutional support, may offer better livelihood opportunities in the flood-affected landscapes of Assam.

Land fragmentation and non-farm labor supply nexus: Evidence from Nepal

Presenter

Prajjwal Dhungana, Research Associate, SANDEE, ICIMOD, Nepal

Co-author(s)

Mani Nepal, Senior Programme Coordinator–SANDEE, ICIMOD, Nepal

Discussant

Arjun Dhakal, Convener, Nepal Network for Social, Development, Economic and Environmental Dialogue (NNSDEE), Nepal

Abstract

In this study, we examined the marginal impact of land fragmentation on the off-farm labour supply in Nepal. Utilising a three-year longitudinal survey data (HRVS) and a separable farm household model with land fragmentation as a form of technical change, we used a Two-way fixed effects (TWFE) panel regression model. We found a negative average effect of land fragmentation on non-farm labour supply; an additional plot reduced non-farm labour supply by 14.06 percentage points. Greater local off-farm opportunities diminished the adverse impact, while no evidence was observed for the moderating impact of machinery on off-farm labour allocation. The effects were significant for the Mountain and Hill regions and were observed only for households with large landholding sizes. Correlation analysis of key production characteristics pointed to reduced labour productivity as an additional potential mechanism. Households appear to respond by increasing farm labour hours, both own and hired, as an adaptation strategy to maintain output levels despite fragmentation. The results were consistent across multiple specifications and robustness tests. The evidence underscores the need for land consolidation and targeted interventions to address reduced labour market imperfections, thereby freeing the surplus labour and accelerating structural transformation in rural Nepal.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 13:30–15:00

PARALLEL SESSION C1

Household energy choices

Chair

Joyashree Roy, Distinguished Professor, Asian Institute of
Technology (AIT), Thailand

Leveraging local mass media: How FM stations' amplify energy access and clean energy use in household

Presenter

Bishal Bharadwaj, Research Associate, University of Calgary, Canada

Discussant

Joyashree Roy, Distinguished Professor, Asian Institute of Technology (AIT), Thailand

Abstract

Studies have explored how social mobilisation, information access, and technologies shape energy decisions, yet the role of local mass media, specifically FM radio stations, in promoting household energy access and clean energy adoption remains underexplored. This study leverages the expansion of FM radio stations across nearly 4,000 villages over 15 years to investigate changes in the adoption of renewable energy technologies (RETs). Using median frequency as an instrumental variable (IV), our analysis reveals that greater exposure to FM radio stations in a village increases biogas and solar home systems (SHS) adoption, with stronger effects from stations within the same district. Analysis of 2011 Census cross-sectional data and three waves of the Nepal Living Standard Survey (NLSS) illustrate FM radio expansion drives clean cooking adoption and higher household energy expenditures. We highlight FM radio stations' role as an information-sharing platform and form of social mobilisation, enabling local clean energy distributors to effectively reach nearby households, thereby enhancing energy access and clean energy adoption.

Nepal's federal transition and rural household cooking fuel choice

Presenter:

Hari Katuwal, Associate Professor, Tarleton State University, USA

Discussant

Krishna Prasad Pant, Visiting Faculty, Kathmandu University, Nepal

Abstract

Using two nationally representative surveys, this paper examines the determinants of households' cooking fuel choice in rural Nepal, considering the effects of the federal transition. Traditional fuel, such as firewood, remains the primary cooking fuel for the majority of Nepal's rural households. The use of traditional fuel causes several environmental and health problems and is inefficient. Given these concerns, the emphasis has shifted from traditional energy to more efficient and cleaner energy sources. Moreover, the 2015 Constitution formally established Nepal as a Federal Democratic Republic. The federal transition significantly reshaped the governance and policy landscape for energy use, moving from a highly centralised system to one with devolved responsibilities across three tiers of government: federal, provincial, and local. However, the impacts of federal transition on cooking fuel choice remain unclear. This study uses pooled data from the two National Living Standards Surveys and Annual Household Surveys in Nepal. We divide cooking fuel into three categories: traditional, transitional, and modern, and use the fuel choice as a dependent variable to estimate the multinomial and ordered logit models. Our results indicate that the household head's education level and household income are positively associated with the use of modern energy, i.e. LPG for cooking. Large families and households in the hill and mountain belt are less likely to use clean fuel. Our pooled model results indicate that the federal transition led to a decrease in transitional cooking fuel use and an increase in modern fuel use in rural households.

Effects of a transition from liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) to induction cookstoves in Kerala Anganwadis, India

Presenter

Praveen Kumar, PhD, Senior Research Fellow Economics and Planning Unit, Indian Statistical Institute Delhi, India

Co-author(s)

Eshita Gupta, Senior Economist, KPMG, Gurugram, India

E. Somanathan, Professor, Economics and Planning Unit, Indian Statistical Institute, India

Fizza Suhel, Sanford School of Public Policy, Duke University, USA

Discussant

Ngawang Dendup, Consultant (Economist), Asian Development Bank Institute (ADBI)

Abstract

Traditional cooking methods remain prevalent, posing risks to both the environment and health. Despite 100% electrification in Indian households, only 5% use some form of electric cooking, indicating a significant potential for scaling up electric cooking in India, as well as in many other countries where this gap exists. This study explores electric cooking with induction cookstoves as an alternative clean cooking solution. Utilising both administrative and survey data within an institutional framework (day care centres) where the initial setup cost of induction cookstoves is subsidised, and applying fixed effects and difference-in-differences models, we find a 10% reduction in LPG consumption and an insignificant but decrease in total cooking time post-intervention. We find a corresponding increase in electricity consumption using administrative data. Our findings show that Anganwadis are saving roughly 300 INR per month on average by partially adopting induction cookstoves. Additionally, we observe that induction cookstoves are not adopted as the sole cooking method but are used alongside LPG. Major barriers to adoption and discontinued adoption include inadequate electricity infrastructure, such as incompatible wiring, sockets, and switchboards, which are likely to be even more challenging in most Indian households.

Adopting solar power for irrigation: Implications for groundwater depletion in Gujarat

Presenter

Praharsh M. Patel, Assistant Professor, Indian Institute of Technology Gandhinagar, India

Discussant

Indira Devi, Professor, Kerala Agricultural University, India

Abstract

Groundwater serves as a vital resource for irrigation in India, underpinning food security and rural livelihoods. To support groundwater-based irrigation, state governments offer substantial energy subsidies, which, while beneficial in the short term, create perverse incentives for over-extraction, driving irreversible groundwater depletion. Although economists advocate price signals as a tool for groundwater conservation, the political economy of the region renders the removal of subsidies infeasible. Grid-connected solar irrigation has emerged as a potential solution, introducing marginal opportunity costs for groundwater usage, but it does not require farmers to pay for it. This study evaluates the impact of such grid-connected solar irrigation under the Suryashakti Kisan Yojna (SKY) scheme, leveraging survey responses from 2,798 farmers. Our findings indicate that the current design of opportunity cost mechanisms linked to solar irrigation adoption falls short of incentivising reduced groundwater extraction. Key barriers include farmers' limited understanding of billing information and on-ground implementation challenges. Additionally, issues such as complex financial calculations and technology failures further hinder the adoption and effectiveness of solar irrigation systems. These findings highlight the need for targeted policy interventions, investing in state capacity to improve service, and better outreach and implementation frameworks to achieve sustainable groundwater management.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 13:30–15:00

PARALLEL SESSION C2

Issues in water management

Chair

Ramesh Ananda Vaidya, Fellow- Senior Advisor (Water and Energy),
ICIMOD, Nepal

Groundwater use in South Asia: The role of technology and water-energy-food-poverty nexus trade-offs

Presenter

Soumya Balasubramanya, Senior Economist, The World Bank, Washington DC, USA

Discussant

Ramesh Ananda Vaidya, Fellow- Senior Advisor (Water and Energy), ICIMOD, Nepal

Abstract

In recent years, the policy discourse in South Asia has increasingly focused on reducing pressure on groundwater use in irrigated agriculture and reducing irrigation energy subsidies, without making farmers worse off. In an environment where pricing water and energy is administratively and politically challenging, much hope is placed on the widespread adoption of irrigation technologies that improve irrigation efficiency. This paper highlights knowledge gaps in this discourse to identify avenues where research could inform evidence-based decision-making.

Urban household's willingness to pay for improved water services

Presenter:

Nirajan Devkota, Research Fellow Policy Research Institute, Government of Nepal, Nepal

Discussant:

Yarzar Hein, Professor and Head of Department, Advanced Center for Agricultural Research and Education, Yezin Agricultural University, Myanmar

Abstract

Water scarcity remains a critical issue in Nepal, as Nepal ranks fifth out of six South Asian nations in 2020, with a national water security score of 52.3 out of 100. Rapid urbanisation and industrialisation have exacerbated this problem, particularly in the Kathmandu Valley, Nepal, straining sustainable water management efforts. This quasi-experimental study assesses water availability, quality, pricing, and household demand for improved water services in Kathmandu Valley, focusing on households' willingness to pay (WTP) for a reliable, piped water supply. Employing contingent valuation methods and difference-in-differences (DiD) analysis, the research reveals a substantial demand for enhanced water services among urban households. The DiD analysis specifically examines the impact of the Melamchi water supply project, finding no significant difference in WTP between households with and without access to Melamchi water. Key findings highlight that household income and the number of family members are positively correlated with WTP. This study suggests that with adequate investment and regulatory focus on water hygiene, both the government and Kathmandu Upatyaka Khanepani Limited (KUKL) can sustainably improve water services. These insights are crucial for developing responsive and effective water management strategies tailored to the needs of Kathmandu Valley's residents.

Willingness to pay for domestic water in Meghalaya: Impact of water poverty and social structure

Presenter

Rida Wanbha Nongbri, Research Scholar, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, India

Co-author(s)

Sabuj Kumar Mandal, Associate Professor, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, India

Discussant: Amjad Ali, Assistant Professor, Department of Development Studies, Karakoram International University Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan

Abstract

Access to improved domestic water supply is crucial for sustainable development, yet many households in Meghalaya, India, struggle with unreliable water services. This study examines household willingness to pay (WTP) for better water access using the contingent valuation method and the Heckman two-stage model to address selection bias. The first stage identifies factors influencing WTP, while the second estimates the amount households are willing to pay. Analysis of 1,050 households shows that higher water poverty reduces WTP, possibly due to reliance on natural sources, while urban and higher-income households are more willing to pay. Matrilineal households show greater willingness, whereas those with in-house piped connections are less likely to contribute. These findings highlight the need for income-sensitive, targeted infrastructure and community-based solutions to improve water access, ensuring affordability while encouraging contributions from those who can pay.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 13:30–15:00

PARALLEL SESSION C3

Environmental governance and growth

Chair

Shiva Raj Adhikari, Professor, Central Department of
Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Discretionary enforcement and strategic compliance experimental evidence

Presenter

Shreekant Gupta, Professor, Delhi School of Economics, India

Co-author(s)

Omer F. Baris, Associate Professor, Nazarbayev University, Graduate School of Public Policy, Kazakhstan

Eduardo Araral Jr, Associate Professor, Lee Kuan Yew School of Public Policy, National University of Singapore, Singapore

Discussant

Resham B. Thapa-Parajuli, Associate Professor, Central Department of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Abstract

We conduct an experimental analysis of the strategic elements of the inspection-compliance game (e.g. between firms and environmental enforcement agencies). We extend the seminal binary-choice (2×2) inspection-compliance game played between an environmental enforcement agency and a firm to a 3×3 game in which both players have additional choices. We experimented (120 rounds) with 164 participants in three countries (India, Kazakhstan, and Singapore). In our model, the Agency strategises over the frequency and quality of inspections and the Firm strategises over compliance behaviour, by investing in non-inspectability in order to deter any inspection or getting caught by the Agency. The results from our laboratory evidence indicate that the availability of strategic non-compliance options reduces overall level of compliance by the firms but increases total inspection although approximately one third of those inspections are just cursory.

Towards sustainable industrialization: The effects of eco-innovation in the environmental sustainability performance of the manufacturing

Presenter

Sadia Islam, Assistant Professor, Dhaka School of Economics, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

Discussant

Mohamed Shumais, The Maldives National University, Maldives

Abstract

The main objective of this study was to examine the impact of eco-innovation on the environmental sustainability performance of the manufacturing sector, with the aim of informing long-term policy development for sustainable industrialisation. To achieve this, primary data were collected from 50 manufacturing units, comprising 30 ready-made garments (RMG) and 20 leather industries. The survey data were analysed using factor analysis to construct indices for environmental sustainability performance, eco-product innovation, and eco-process innovation. Subsequently, a classical linear regression model was employed to test the hypotheses. The empirical findings indicate a positive relationship between eco-innovation and environmental sustainability performance within the manufacturing sector. In particular, eco-product innovation demonstrated a significant positive impact, whereas eco-process innovation showed no significant effect on environmental sustainability performance.

Stand characteristics in relation to forest management regimes and disturbance gradients in Tropical Forest Ecosystems

Presenter

Mohammad Belal Uddin, Professor, Department of Forestry and Environmental Science, Shahjalal University of Science and Technology, Bangladesh

Discussant

To be added

Abstract

Forests of Bangladesh are highly threatened by anthropogenic disturbances, even within the protected areas. This study explores how species richness, basal area, and regeneration status vary with different intensities of disturbances as well as the protection status of a Bangladesh forest site. A total of 65 permanent plots of (20x20) m were positioned arbitrarily without preconceived bias for field information collection. In each sample plot necessary data, e.g. tree count, DBH and regeneration, were collected, while the nature and intensities of the presence of anthropogenic and natural disturbances were quantified visually and from key informants. One-way ANOVA and post hoc pair wise Tukey HSD mean separation test, along with homogeneity of variance test ($P=0.05$) were used in data analysis. Result shows that species richness, basal area and regeneration vary with the three forest management regimes and disturbance intensities. With increased trend of protection status, disturbance decreased. Thus, forest managers and conservation biologist should be more diplomatic to choose management strategy to conserve country's remaining forest stocks from human interference.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 13:30–15:00

PARALLEL SESSION C4

Gender and energy transition

Chair

Pranab Mukhopadhyay, Senior Professor, Goa University, India

Electrifying empowerment: Women and energy access

Presenter

Subhrendu K. Pattanayak, Oak Foundation Distinguished Professor of Environmental and Energy Policy, Duke University, USA

Discussant

Atonu Rabbani, Professor, Department of Economics, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abstract

Most of us woke up this morning, used energy and technology to learn about the weather and the news, got a fresh cup of coffee, and went about our day informed and refreshed. Imagine if every woman in a poor, remote village could access technology for vital information the same way. Yet, they cannot. Lack of energy access disempowers women. This presentation (and paper) begins by reviewing what we know and what we do not know, from applied empirical research, about the different ways in which energy access empowers women. An important conclusion is the two-way relationship between women's empowerment and the adoption and use of clean energy technologies, and the challenge of causal research. The second part of the presentation (and paper) describes a series of coordinated studies to measure women's agency and empowerment in Africa and Asia, with special attention to time use. Finally, the presentation (paper) focuses on a specific randomised control trial in Myanmar, bracketed first by COVID and then a coup. We consider the question that in many settings, gender norms relegate women to domestic roles, which, in turn, may erode their sense of agency across many life domains and lower their aspirations. This may further discourage them from pursuing fruitful opportunities, including clean energy investments, which could ease women's disproportionate burden from household work and raise their productive potential. We ran a randomised control trial in the states of Ayeyarwady and Tanintharyi of Myanmar to test a psychological empowerment intervention that combines an 'edutainment' component with a series of visualisation, goal setting and planning exercises drawn from motivational psychology. The intervention was highly successful at raising women's empowerment, particularly on dimensions (financial and business agency) most salient in the story. However, we only see positive effects on aspirations for productive appliances and for children's education in unelectrified villages, where we also see a matching increase in education expenditures, the time women spend on childcare, and the probability that households took out a business loan. We argue that a harder path to higher education in these areas means that there is still a larger share of people who can be influenced by the education-focused component of the edutainment story. These effects are driven by the more ambitious, empowered, and educated women, suggesting that which subgroups and which dimensions of aspirations respond to the intervention depend on how feasible those aspirations feel. The presentation (papers) concludes with lessons for research and for policy, not just from this trial in Myanmar, but also the coordinated studies and the systematic reviews, about the links between empowerment and energy access.

Impact of indoor air pollution on child wellbeing

Presenter

Heman Das Lohano, Visiting Professor, Department of Applied Economics, University of Minnesota, USA

Discussant

Pranab Mukhopadhyay, Senior Professor, Goa University, India

Abstract

Indoor air pollution poses a significant threat to child wellbeing, as children typically spend a considerable amount of time indoors and are more vulnerable to air pollution than adults. Cooking with polluting fuels, including biomass (wood, animal dung, and crop waste), lignite coal, charcoal, and kerosene, represents a major source of indoor household air pollution. This study evaluates the impact of indoor household air pollution on morbidity in children under 5 years of age in Pakistan using quasi-experimental methods. The results indicate that 49% of households in Pakistan primarily rely on polluting fuel for cooking, while the remaining 51% use cleaner fuels such as natural gas, LPG, electricity, or biogas. The empirical findings reveal that the probability of Acute Respiratory Infection (ARI) symptoms in children increases by 2.40 percentage points if the household uses polluting fuel for cooking. Moreover, the probability of ARI symptoms in children decreases by 1.99 percentage points if the household has a separate kitchen room for cooking. Additionally, the probability of ARI symptoms in children decreases by 2.53 percentage points if there is no tobacco smoking inside the house. We also find empirical evidence that the probability of mortality in children increases by 1.42 percentage points if the household uses polluting fuel for cooking. The findings of this study underscore the crucial role of household behaviour in averting exposure to indoor household air pollution and reducing the associated health risks.

Women's bargaining power and energy consumption in Myanmar

Presenter

Zin Nwe Win, Country Manager, Sierra Leone & Liberia, Innovations for Poverty Action

Co-author(s)

Subhrendu K. Pattanayak, Oak Foundation Distinguished Professor of Environmental and Energy Policy, Duke University, USA

Ferran Vega-Carol, PhD Student, Duke University, USA

Mani Nepal, Senior Programme Coordinator–SANDEE, ICIMOD, Nepal

Thein Zaw Oo, Independent Consultant

Discussant

Shiba Satyal Banskota, Gender Equality and Social Inclusion Lead, ICIMOD, Nepal

Abstract

Our study delves into a bidirectional relationship between women empowerment and clean energy adoption. Using survey data gathered on 1,155 households across 66 rural villages in the delta and coastal regions of Myanmar, we look at the differences in the level of electricity access and patterns of use between two types of villages: off-grid solar mini-grid villages and non-electrified (non mini-grid) villages. Furthermore, we examine how the benefits from access are distributed across genders. In doing so, we explore the relation between gender attitudes and measures of women empowerment and the patterns of adoption of clean energy poverty-reducing technologies. To do so, we utilised both survey measures and behavioural experimental methods (such as bargaining and choice games). In a subsample of 32 villages, we also conducted a follow-up Vickrey second-price auction using solar lamps with lighting and charging facilities to measure the demand for clean energy. Through this study, we aim to contribute to the sparse empirical literature on the gender-energy nexus, and in particular on the role of gender in the adoption of clean energy technologies in low- and middle-income countries.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 13:30–15:00

PARALLEL SESSION C5

Environmental pollution

Chair

Bhupesh Adhikary, Climate Action Lead, ICIMOD, Nepal

Farmer's preferences for different crop residue management practices: Evidence from choice experiment in Punjab India

Presenter

Eshita Gupta, Senior Economist, KPMG, Gurugram, India

Co-author(s)

Subham Agarwal, Senior consultant, KPMG, Gurugram, India

Damini Thakur, Associate Director, KPMG, Gurugram, India

Shibanjan Dutta, Manager, KPMG, Gurugram, India

Heena Sharma, Monitoring and Evaluation expert, The Nature Conservancy, India

James Erbaugh, Applied Social Scientist, The Nature Conservancy, USA

Rajveer Singh, Agronomist, The Nature Conservancy, India

Gurpreet Singh, Regenerative Agriculture, Diageo, Bangalore, India

Priya Shyamsundar, Senior Economist, The Nature Conservancy, India

Discussant

Bhupesh Adhikary, Climate Action Lead, ICIMOD, Nepal

Abstract

This study examines farmers' preferences for no-burn crop residue management (CRM) technologies in Punjab, India, through a choice experiment involving 1,339 farmers across 10 districts. Results reveal that farmers prioritise certain attributes, including the type of CRM machine, service provider, and technical advisory, but not technology access wait time. A preference for Incorporation & Mulching via Smart Seeder over other methods was noted, with Custom Hiring Centers as the preferred service providers and a favor for combined digital and physical advisory. Wealthier farmers showed less interest in non-burn CRM alternatives. The findings suggest a general willingness among farmers to adopt no-burn CRM practices, highlighting the importance of targeted interventions to promote sustainable agriculture.

State mediated trade, distortions and air pollution

Presenter

Digvijay Singh Negi, Associate Professor, Ashoka University, India

Discussant

Mohammad Iftekharul Islam, Research Assistant, South Asian Network on Economic Modeling (SANEM), Bangladesh

Abstract

Can government-imposed market integration and resultant specialisation contribute to a large-scale negative environmental externality? I compare agricultural fire activity and air pollution levels in districts where the government interferes in the local grain markets with districts without such interference to establish a link between food prices and air pollution in India. This link comes about due to higher prices leading to increased agricultural fire activity in districts where the government procures foodgrains from the local markets. Estimates suggest a 19% increase in out-of-pocket medical expenditure associated with higher air pollution. The mortality cost of resultant pollution is USD 1 billion larger than gains to producers from higher prices.

Fire in the fields, crime in the air

Presenter

Hardeep Singh, Assistant Professor, Indian Institute of Technology Jammu, India

Co-author(s)

Digvijay S. Negi, Associate Professor, Ashoka University, India

Discussant

Tshotsho, Lecturer, College of Natural Resources, Royal University of Bhutan, Bhutan

Abstract

We exploit seasonal crop residue burning as a source of pollution and use exogenous year-to-year variation in wind direction to estimate the impact of rural sources of air pollution on crime in India. We find that short-term pollution exposure leads to an increase in violent crime, public order offenses, and most worryingly, violent crimes against women. Estimates suggest an unaccounted social cost of USD 600 million just from pollution exposure in the rice harvest season. We explore three channels: (i) pollution induced aggression and weakened impulse control, (ii) reduced visibility leading to poor deterrence, and (iii) income distress from reduced earnings. Heterogeneity by crime type and spatial variation in law enforcement capacity support these mechanisms. Our findings highlight the need to account for issues of public safety and social instability in environmental and agricultural policy in developing countries.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 15:30–17:00

PARALLEL SESSION D1

Environmental governance II

Chair

Yi Shaoliang, Senior Intervention Manager-Rangelands and Wetlands, ICIMOD, Nepal

Empowering youth through engagement in environmental problem-solving: A case study of the Kutupalong Rohingya Refugee Camp in Bangladesh

Presenter

Rumi Shammin, David Orr Professor, Environmental Studies & Sciences Program, Oberlin College, USA

Discussant

Yi Shaoliang, Senior Intervention Manager-Rangelands and Wetlands, ICIMOD, Nepal

Abstract

Can disadvantaged youth in underserved communities be engaged in environmental problem-solving as a win-win solution? The Kutupalong refugee camp, where more than 700,000 refugees are being accommodated, provides shelter to more than 70,000 refugees between the ages of 12 to 17. These youth living in the camps through their formative years are among the most underserved refugees with no access to education, vocational training, or work opportunities. At the same time, environmental issues and solutions often take a back seat in refugee response initiatives, which generally prioritise humanitarian services. This case study presents a unique initiative undertaken by IUCN to involve youth groups in multiple environmental problem-solving projects for over three years. The win-win outcomes constitute empowerment of refugee youth and low-cost community-based environmental solutions. Lessons from the refugee youth engagement inside camps can potentially be replicated in disadvantaged communities elsewhere and aligned with multiple sustainable development goals (SDGs).

Assessing well-being and sustainability of small-scale fishing communities in Nepal

Presenter

Thaneshwar Bhandari, Assistant Professor, Institute of Agriculture and Animal Science, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Discussant

Indrila Guha, Principal and Head of Department, Department of Economics, Basanti Devi College, India

Abstract

While small-scale fisheries have gained increased attention in recent years, previous studies have not thoroughly examined the well-being and sustainability status of fishing communities. This study aims to address these gaps by assessing the socioeconomic status of fishing activities, estimating sustainable economic well-being, and evaluating its key determinants. A structured survey was conducted among randomly selected 126 fishers in six districts of Nepal – Bara, Chitwan, Dhanusha, Kaski, Makawanpur, and Rupandehi – to assess well-being and sustainability through quantitative and qualitative indicators and respondents' perception of life satisfaction, fishing-related satisfaction, and both market and non-market dimensions of well-being. Key analyses included descriptive statistics, estimation of sustainable economic welfare, assessment of qualitative well-being indicators, and ranking of welfare determinants. The findings revealed an average change in wealth (ΔW) of NPR -117,185, indicating a net decline. Approximately 67% of fishers experienced unsustainable wealth earning over the two-year period (2023-2024), while only 24% were found to be operating sustainably. Most fishers reported significant struggles in maintaining economic assets, raising concerns about the long-term viability of their livelihoods. As the majority were small-scale fishers, they expressed dissatisfaction with income levels, poor governance, and limited access to alternative livelihoods. The top five determinants influencing fishers' welfare were climatic vulnerabilities, illegal fishing and removal of river debris, weaker policies including harmful subsidies, water pollution and human-wildlife conflicts. To improve the welfare of small-scale fishing communities, the study recommends targeted interventions in economic diversification, sociocultural empowerment, health and nutrition improvements, environmental conservation, and comprehensive governance and policy reforms.

Clean fuel use, political representation and forest cover: Evidence from rural India

Presenter

Prasenjit Sarkhel, Professor, Department of Economics, University of Kalyani, India

Co-author(s)

Samarpita Ghosh, Department of Economics, University of Kalyani, India

Discussant

Monjit Borthakur, Assistant Professor, Department of Geography, Cotton University, Assam, India

Abstract

This paper examines how political representation for marginalised groups affects development outcomes and environmental choices by studying the adoption of clean cooking fuels under India's Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana (PMUY). Focusing on political reservations for Scheduled Tribes (STs), we assess how these institutional arrangements influence household fuel use across ecologically diverse regions. Using village-level data from the 2020 Mission Antyodaya Survey and high-resolution forest cover data, we employ a spatial regression discontinuity design (SRD) to compare LPG adoption between Scheduled Areas (administratively designated tribal-majority regions) and non-Scheduled Areas. We find that ST political reservations at the assembly constituency level are associated with a significant reduction in PMUY uptake in Scheduled Areas. To explore variation within SAs, we employ Propensity Score Matching to assess the impact of the Panchayat Extension to Scheduled Areas Act (PESA), which mandates ST representation in local governance. We find that PESA increases LPG adoption in villages located in open forest and scrubland, while it reduces uptake in regions with moderately dense forests. Additionally, our analysis reveals that higher forest cover displaces clean fuel use, and quantile regressions confirm that PESA implementation is linked to forest gains –suggesting that politically empowered ST leaders may promote conservation, inadvertently reinforcing biomass dependence. Our findings highlight a policy trade-off between environmental stewardship and the clean energy transition in ecologically sensitive tribal areas.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 15:30–17:00

PARALLEL SESSION D2

Climate adaptation and mitigation

Chair

Randall Bluffstone, Professor of Economics and Director of the Institute for Economics and the Environment, Portland State University, USA

A cross-country and long-term evaluation of UNFCC climate change adaptation projects

Presenter

Saudamini Das, Professor in Economics, Institute of Economic Growth, Delhi, India

Co-author(s)

Yusuph John Kulindwa, Associate Professor, Moshi Cooperative University, Moshi, Tanzania

Discussant

David Potter, Head of Regional Action and Global Advocacy, ICIMOD, Nepal

Abstract

Multilateral projects for advancing climate change adaptation in developing countries mandate that women do some percentage of the work. However, systematic evaluation of these mandates on women's empowerment has been limited. This study evaluates two similar climate change adaptation projects, implemented by the UNFCC's Adaptation Fund Board (AFB) in India and Tanzania, by measuring their impact on women's empowerment after six to seven years of their completion. These projects were mandated to achieve at least 33% of project work done by women in India and to make women the primary beneficiaries in Tanzania. The project sites were the Krishna district of Andhra Pradesh state in India and the Kigamboni municipal council of the Dar Es Salaam region in Tanzania. We study the beneficiaries and the non-beneficiaries in project sites and employ the asset index (ASI) and women's empowerment index (WEI) as impact indicators. Propensity Score Matching and Endogenous Switching Regression techniques are used to measure the average treatment effects. We find the impacts on asset holding to be weak, but strong and significant on women's empowerment, though the results vary across the countries.

Quantifying noneconomic losses and damages in Sindh post 2022 floods

Presenter

Lubna Naz, Professor and Director, Center for Business and Economic Research, Institute of Business Administration Karachi, Pakistan

Co-author(s)

Saima Saif, Assistant Professor, Institute of Business Administration, Pakistan

Zaheer Ali, Assistant Professor, Institute of Business Administration, Pakistan

Discussant

Randall Bluffstone, Professor of Economics and Director of the Institute for Economics and the Environment, Portland State University, USA

Abstract

This study investigates the non-economic losses and damages (NELD) in the flood-prone districts of Sindh, Pakistan, resulting from the 2022 floods. While traditional assessments focus on economic losses, this research emphasises the often-overlooked impacts on psychological well-being, loss of life, ecosystem services, and social displacement. A mixed-method approach was used, combining quantitative tools such as the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale (DASS-21) and the World Health Organization Quality of Life Brief Scale (WHOQOL-Brief) with qualitative methods, Key Informant Interviews, to assess NELD. The findings highlight significant psychological distress among the affected populations, especially women and children, with widespread anxiety and depression, underscoring the need for enhanced mental health support during and after floods. The KII substantiate the results from the psychological assessment and identifies various risk factors, including poor health and safety, social and economic insecurity, inadequate response and resilience, and loss of cultural properties and ecosystem services.

Perceived adverse impacts undermine limited socio-economic benefits of resin tapping from Chirpine forests

Presenter

Rajan Parajuli, Associate Professor, North Carolina State University, USA

Discussant

Kishor Atreya, Associate Professor, Institute of Forestry, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Abstract

Chirpine (*Pinus roxburghii*), also known as longleaf Indian pine, is the most tapped pine species in several Asian countries, including Nepal, for its high resin yield. Resin tapping in Chirpine trees has been a longstanding practice in the mid-hills of Nepal for the last several decades. This study aimed to evaluate the social impacts of resin tapping from Chirpine forests on the rural socio-ecological dynamics of Nepal's mid-hills. Using a representative sample of 302 forest users from 20 community forest user groups in three far-western districts, we applied the structural equation modelling approach to examine both the positive and negative perceived effects of resin tapping on the rural livelihoods. While respondents acknowledged the positive impacts of resin tapping on local employment and community development activities, many respondents stressed the negative environmental outcomes, including increased fire incidents, water scarcity, and higher mortality of pine trees. Results suggest that rich and male respondents are less likely to realise the negative impacts of resin tapping, whereas a member of community forest user groups is more likely to view resin tapping favourably. Understanding the perspectives of forest users on resin tapping within evolving socio-ecological dynamics shaped by changing social, demographic, and economic factors is critical for ensuring the sustainability of Chirpine-based human-nature interactions.

The rapid economic recovery from earthquake relief to reconstruction: A case study of the January 7, 2025 Dingri earthquake, Xizang, China

Presenter

Bingwei Tian, Associate Professor, Assistant Dean, PHD, IDMR, Sichuan University, China

Discussant

Nirmal Kumar Raut, Associate Professor, Central Department of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Abstract

Earthquake recovery in high-altitude regions is often considered slow and fragile, and research on such settings remains limited. The Dingri earthquake on January 7, 2025, showed a different pattern: despite geographic constraints and limited resources, the affected area moved from emergency response to the early resumption of economic activities in a relatively continuous way. Using publicly available information and a process-tracing approach, this study examines this recovery trajectory and proposes a continuous chain linking response, restoration, reconstruction, and economic recovery. Three mechanisms are identified: institutional mobilisation, infrastructure restoration, and economic resilience. The findings show that the rapid restoration of basic connectivity – especially roads and communication – played a central role in shaping the overall pace of recovery. The flexible nature of local economic sectors, including farming, herding, border trade, and tourism, further supported the early return of economic activities. A comparison with international earthquake cases suggests that the Dingri process does not simply fit existing models but reflects a context-specific mechanism shaped by altitude, connectivity, and local industry characteristics. The results offer a new perspective on post-earthquake recovery in extreme environments and point to the need for future studies using micro-level data and scenario-based models to further test the proposed framework.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 15:30–17:00

PARALLEL SESSION D3 |

Topics in environmental economics I

Chair

Jón Geir Pétursson, Professor Environment and Natural Resources,
Interdisciplinary Graduate Programme, University of Iceland, Iceland

Climate variability and household electricity consumption

Presenter

Rosalina Palanca-Tan, Professor, Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines

Co-author(s)

Gerald Gracius Y. Pascua, Lecturer, Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines

Discussant

Jón Geir Pétursson, Professor Environment and Natural Resources, Interdisciplinary Graduate Programme, University of Iceland, Iceland

Abstract

This study aims to inform evidence-based policy for climate change adaptation in the Philippines by estimating the climate sensitivity of household electricity demand in Metro Manila. Using a panel of monthly household electricity consumption data from 2001 to 2021, matched with climate data from the Philippine Atmospheric Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration, the study constructs heat index (HI) measures and Cooling Degree Days (CDD) to capture climate variability. The HI, which combines temperature and relative humidity to reflect perceived heat discomfort, is averaged monthly across three monitoring stations and matched to households' city of residence. CDD, defined as the number of days when daily HI exceeds a long-run threshold of 34.82°C (the 75th percentile of historical HI), is used as an indicator of climate variability. Panel regressions using random-effects generalised least squares reveal strong climate sensitivity of electricity consumption in Metro Manila households. A 1°C increase in average daily temperature is associated with a 38 kWh increase in monthly electricity use, while a 1°C rise in HI leads to a 19 kWh increase. An additional CDD raises monthly consumption by 6 kWh. These findings suggest behavioural adjustments, such as increased use of electric fans and air-conditioners, during hotter periods. However, electricity demand among lower-income households is significantly less responsive to climate fluctuations, likely due to budget constraints and limited access to cooling technologies. This implies greater exposure to heat-related health risks and highlights the inequitable non-market costs of climate change. Conversely, higher-income households show greater responsiveness, indicating potential for targeted promotion of energy-efficient appliances and rooftop solar adoption within this group. The results underscore the importance of climate-sensitive energy policies that address both mitigation and equity concerns.

Macroeconomic analysis of green monetary policy in India's emission mitigation: Evidence from Wallace neutrality

Presenter

Sayar Ahmad Shah, PhD Scholar, Indian Institute of Technology Ropar, Punjab, India

Co-author(s)

Bhavesh Garg, Assistant Professor, Indian Institute of Technology Ropar, Punjab, India

Discussant

V. Saravanakumar, Professor, Agricultural Economics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India

Abstract

This study investigates the significance of green quantitative easing in emission mitigation. In a DSGE approach featuring both macroeconomic and environmental sectors, we simulate a market-neutral monetary policy and an unconventional green monetary policy to study the effect of green quantitative easing. The analysis provides that in the presence of financial frictions and elasticity imperfections, a green monetary policy is able to mitigate emissions. We found that a green quantitative easing that is tilted towards the green asset purchase (i.e. bonds issued by the non-polluting sector) contributes efficiently towards a reduction in CO₂ emissions. The findings of the present study can serve as the gauge for the environmentally sensitive central banks in designing appropriate monetary policy for emission mitigation.

Do international remittances enhance credit repayability and reshape labor supply among households with international migrants in Nepal?

Presenter

Sumant Kumar Yadav, Master Student, Hiroshima University, Japan

Co-author(s)

Niraj Prakash Joshi, Associate Professor, Hiroshima University, Japan

Keshav Lall Maharjan, Professor, Hiroshima University, Japan

Discussant

Gopal Tiwari, General Secretary of Nepal Economic Association, Nepal

Abstract

The increase in international migration from Nepal is attributable to a complex interaction of domestic economic challenges and compelling global attracting factors. The combined effect of economic difficulties within local communities and the rising demand in the global labour market motivates Nepali individuals to seek improved opportunities abroad and lift their families out of poverty, which leads to a few challenges, such as land abandonment and feminisation of agriculture in the origin country. Rural households also face limited formal credit access, so they depend on informal credit, which poses repayment challenges. This study aims to assess how international remittances affect households' credit repayment and labour supply. Using data from the Nepal Household Risk and Vulnerability Survey (2016), 1,770 households with international migrants were analysed. The study addresses the endogeneity of remittance receipt using foreign exchange rate fluctuations as an instrumental variable (IV), meeting conditions of relevance, exogeneity, and exclusion restriction criteria. The IV-2SLS method establishes causality between remittances and outcomes. Receiving international remittances enhances household credit repayment by 1.14 points and reduces daily labour supply by 3.16 hours. There is also a differential impact on credit repayment ability among households by the type of loan borrowed. Households with informal loans improve credit repayability by 1.36 points, significant at 1%. Overall, international remittance acts as a financial safety net for Nepalese households, improving creditworthiness by enhancing repayability. The reduction in daily labour, especially in wage and non-agricultural sectors, indicates the income effect is strong, with remittance reducing the need for physically demanding, low-return jobs. Policies should focus on remittance-based credit access via formal institutions with flexible repayment and recognise remittance as collateral. Additionally, transforming subsistence agriculture into an agri-entrepreneurial model and promoting agricultural mechanisation can attract youth and address labour loss.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 15:30–17:00

PARALLEL SESSION D4

Natural disasters

Chair

Orapan Srisawalak, Professor Emeritus, Sukhothai Thammathirat Open University, Thailand

Impact of climatic shocks and coping strategies on livelihood: Evidence from the coastal Bangladesh

Presenter

Pallab Mozumder, Associate Professor, Florida International University, USA

Co-author(s)

Monoj Kumar Majumder, Associate Professor, Sher-e-Bangla Agricultural University, Bangladesh

Discussant

Orapan Srisawalak, Professor Emeritus, Sukhothai Thammathirat Open University, Thailand

Abstract

The incidence of natural disasters has been increasing globally in recent decades, mainly due to climate change. Bangladesh is considered one of the most vulnerable countries in Southeast Asia, facing the adverse effects of global climate change. Among the various natural disasters and hazards, intense floods are occurring more frequently and adversely affecting households' livelihoods. The main objective of this study is to explore the impact of floods on the household's income, expenditure and land ownership. Our empirical findings show that flood shock reduces household income, expenditure and land ownership by 13.89%, 14.6% and 33.6%, respectively. In addition, this study explores different coping strategies to cope with the adverse impact of flood shock and finds that different coping strategies make the adverse impact of flood insignificant. Among the coping strategies, credit positively and significantly increases the household's income, expenditure and land ownership among the flood-affected households. From our empirical data, we find that households' income, expenditure, and land ownership increase by about 32%, 30%, and 17% with credit than the households that did not take any coping strategies, respectively. The study also finds that credit is more effective with severe flood shock. The government should implement and regulate credit policies so that the coastal region's people can use credit to cope with climate shocks in a better way.

Paved to nowhere: The dubious payoffs of Nepal's rural road expansion

Presenter

Santosh Adhikari, Assistant Professor and Program Coordinator, Kathmandu University, Nepal

Discussant

Raghu Bir Bista, Associate Professor, Department of Economics, Patan Multiple Campus, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Abstract

Using household survey data from Nepal, we estimate plot and household panel models to assess the impact of road proximity on economic outcomes. Plot level regressions for land values and following yield largely insignificant or counterintuitive results, with only the wet-season following model showing a 0.57 percentage-point increase in following probability per additional kilometre from an earthen road. Household-level models for crop production value, livestock holdings, farm income, and non-farm income likewise indicate that greater remoteness is associated with higher returns, remaining statistically significant in most specifications. Ward-level analysis of landslide risk finds that a one-kilometre reduction in distance to newly constructed earthen roads corresponds to a 1.8% increase in landslide-area share, while blacktopped roads have no significant effect and rainfall interactions attenuate significance. These findings suggest that road expansion in rugged terrains such as Nepal's can become a lose-lose proposition, leading to environmental hazards without substantial economic benefits.

When the rain stops, do rings come early? Rainfall shocks and child marriage in Nepal

Presenter

Adish Karki, Undergrad Student (Senior), Kathmandu University, Nepal

Co-author(s):

Sushant Rijal, Student, Kathmandu University, Nepal

Discussant:

Ratna Kumar Jha, Research fellow, Food and Agriculture Organisation, United Nations, Nepal

Abstract

This study looks at how droughts affect child marriage in Nepal, especially for boys and girls separately. Using national DHS data linked with detailed climate data from NASA, we examine how long dry periods (droughts) impact when children get married. We find that droughts generally reduce the chances of child marriage. However, this effect is weaker—or even reversed—for girls. In fact, during extreme droughts (when the Standardised Precipitation Index is ≤ -1.5), the chances of girls being married off actually increase, while the chances go down for boys. This suggests that girls face more pressure during tough times, likely because families rely on early marriage as a way to cope with financial stress and cultural expectations. Our findings show how climate shocks and gender norms combine to affect children's lives, especially girls. This points to the need for policies that protect girls in areas affected by climate change. Overall, our study highlights that the reasons behind child marriage during droughts can be very different for boys and girls, likely due to differences in social roles, economic pressures, or how families respond to hardship.

Shadows of shock: Natural disasters and the dynamics of economic growth and recovery in South Asian countries

Presenter

Abina VP, PhD Scholar, Institute for Social and Economic Change, India

Co-author(s)

Meenakshi Rajeev, Professor, Indian Institute of Technology, Jammu, India

Discussant

Ridish Pokharel, Professor of Forestry, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Abstract

Despite being one of the most disaster-prone regions in the world, South Asia has received relatively limited scholarly attention regarding the macroeconomic consequences of such events. Therefore, the present study attempts to fill this gap by analysing both the short and long-term impacts of natural disasters in the region. Drawing on panel data for South Asian countries over the period 1980–2024, this study employs a twofold empirical strategy: the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to estimate the short to long-term growth effects, and an event study approach to assess the recovery path following major disaster episodes. The findings of the study reveal that, on average, major disaster events lead to a decline in GDP per capita growth by 0.75 percentage points (p.p.) and an output loss of 2.41 p.p. in the short run. Furthermore, in the presence of a long-run relationship among the variables, the results show that any deviation from the long-run equilibrium is corrected at an adjustment speed of -0.531. However, the considerable heterogeneity in medium-term recovery patterns indicates that natural disasters are fundamentally a development challenge for South Asian countries. Notably, half of these countries remain below their pre-disaster growth rates even after five years, highlighting the urgent need to strengthen institutional capacity and invest in resilient infrastructure to facilitate faster recovery and sustained long-term growth.

DAY 03

Sunday, 14 December 2025 | 15:30–17:00

PARALLEL SESSION D5

Topics in environmental economics II

Chair

Gunnar Köhlin, Director, Environment for Development
Associate Professor, School of Business, Economics and Law,
University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, **Sweden**

SANDEE family from Pakistan@2025: Achievements and leadership development in environment economics

Presenter

Khuda Bakhsh, Professor, Cotton University, Guwahati, India

Discussant

Gunnar Köhlin, Director, Environment for Development Associate Professor, School of Business, Economics and Law, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden

Abstract

Like other South Asian countries, Pakistan is facing a number of challenges relating to the environment and climate change. These changes include deforestation, soil and water degradation (water shortage), industrial waste, etc. in addition to climate change threats in the forms of floods, drought and earthquakes. Environmental economics in Pakistan was given attention by a few universities in the early years of the first decade of the 21st century. The economists from Pakistan started giving attention to environmental economics around the years when SANDEE started its journey. Since the aim of the SANDEE programs is to attract young and early-career economists, economists were eager to become part of the SANDEE programs. Although the number in the early life of SANDEE was not too high, the participation of a few economists motivated the fellows and budding economists to work in the field of environmental economics. Many made efforts to be members of the SANDEE family. The number of SANDEE grantees is above 30, and many more attended different training workshops and the courses offered by SANDEE. There was a time in many universities when the head of the departments used to say that environment-related courses should be taught by those affiliated with SANDEE, either a grantee or participant of any training course/workshop. This shows the credibility of the training courses offered by SANDEE. Further, by looking at the profiles of the SANDEE family, I find that many grantees are playing a leadership role in building the capacity of young economists and the economics departments in different universities. Findings of the publications are discussed during policy discussions at various levels in Pakistan. Even some are among the policymakers in the climate change ministry. This study is designed to evaluate the performance, contributions, achievements and leadership role in the subject of environmental economics and climate change. I compare these indicators of SANDEE grantees with those of not having affiliation with SANDEE. Findings provide important and useful insights of achievements and leadership role in building capacity of young economists in environmental economics.

Effectiveness of fiscal policy for forest conservation and restoration in Indian States

Presenter

Amarendra Das, Associate Professor, National Institute of Science Education and Research (NISER) Bhubaneswar, India

Co-author(s)

Dinesh Kumar Nayak, Economist, NIPFP, New Delhi, India

Sanjay Kumar Rout, Project Scientist, DST-CPR, NISER Bhubaneswar, India

Discussant

EPN Udayakumara, Professor, Sabaragamuwa University of Sri Lanka, Sri Lanka

Abstract

This research examines the impact of government expenditure on forestry and wildlife and the effect of policy shifts post-2012 on forest cover across 28 Indian states from 2000 to 2023. Given India's commitment to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and its evolving forest conservation policies, this study explores the relationship between fiscal transfers from the Union Government and forest cover changes. Using econometric models, including the Fixed Effects model, the analysis identifies a positive correlation between government spending in the forestry sector and increased forest cover, though the relationship varies across periods and model specifications. The research highlights the role of policy changes and increased fiscal transfers after the 12th Finance Commission's recommendations in 2012, with significant improvements in forest cover observed post-2012. However, the study also reveals that, despite rising expenditure, the growth rate of spending in the forestry sector has generally lagged behind the total expenditure of states, indicating that forestry has not been prioritised in state budgets. The findings underscore the need for more targeted and prioritised budgetary allocations for forest conservation and wildlife protection, particularly in light of India's ongoing environmental challenges. This research contributes to the broader discussion on the effectiveness of fiscal transfers and policy shifts in achieving sustainable forest management and conservation goals in India.

Consumers' attitude towards food waste reduction and projecting Its econo-environmental benefits

Presenter

Tasnim Murad Mamun, Associate Professor, Economics Discipline, Khulna University, Bangladesh

Co-author(s)

Puspendu Debnath, Student, Economics discipline, Khulna University, Bangladesh

Sabrina Akter, Lecturer, Economics discipline, Khulna University, Bangladesh

Discussant

Yamini Gupta, Professor, University of Delhi, India

Abstract

Food waste poses a significant challenge to global sustainability, impacting food security, environmental integrity, and economic development. This study investigates the behavioural determinants influencing consumers' attitudes towards food waste reduction and projects the potential economic and environmental benefits of minimising food waste in Khulna City Corporation (KCC), Bangladesh. Utilising primary data from 400 households through structured questionnaires, the study applies Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) to assess the impact of variables such as environmental consciousness, health awareness, social influence, religious belief, attitude, and food purchasing behaviour on food waste reduction behaviour. The results reveal that environmental consciousness, religious belief, social influence, food purchasing behaviour, and general attitude significantly influence food waste reduction, whereas health consciousness shows an insignificant impact. Additionally, the study calculates potential compost generation and CO₂ emission reductions from household food waste. Based on projected population growth up to 2050, findings estimate a significant increase in food waste if unaddressed, but also demonstrate substantial benefits from compost production and reduced dependency on chemical fertilisers. The study emphasises the role of consumers' ethical and cultural values in shaping waste-related behaviour and highlights the importance of circular economy practices to promote sustainability. By connecting behavioural analysis with environmental and economic projections, this research offers valuable insights for policymakers, local governments, and sustainability advocates. The findings advocate for targeted awareness campaigns, religious and social mobilisation, and sustainable consumption policies to reduce food waste and support Bangladesh's sustainable development goals.

Demand for clean air increases with pollution abatement success

Presenter

Jin Yana, Assistant Professor, Peking University, China

Discussant

Chandan Singha, Associate Professor, Hindu College, University of Delhi, India

Abstract

Despite substantial air quality improvements in China over the past decade, public demand for further pollution reduction has unexpectedly increased. We document this phenomenon using identical discrete choice experiments administered in 2016 and 2024. We find that the average willingness to pay (WTP) for reducing mortality and morbidity risks increased by over 60%, even as ambient fine particulate matter concentrations fell by 58%. This finding is robust; the increase in WTP is not explained by potential confounding effects from the pandemic or by a diminishing marginal utility of money. Instead, our analysis suggests the heightened demand is partly driven by a significant improvement in the perceived credibility of the government's ability to implement air quality policies. Contrary to static predictions of diminishing marginal WTP, we find demand for environmental quality grows with policy credibility, even after substantial cleanup. They underscore the critical need to regularly update valuations in benefit-cost analysis and demonstrate that institutional credibility is a key determinant in stated preference outcomes.

Full agenda

Full programme

All timestamps are in Nepal Standard Time (NPT)

Day 01 | Friday, 12 December 2025

Time (NPT)	Topic
08:30–09:00	Registration
09:00–10:30	Dissemination workshop on Economics of forest restoration as carbon mitigation and Nature-based Solutions in South Asia Moderator: Mani Nepal (Open for all SANDEE@25 participants) Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room
10:30–11:00	Photo session Tea/coffee break
11:00–12:30	Panel discussion on Economics of forest restoration as carbon mitigation and Nature-based Solutions in South Asia Moderator: Soumya Balasubramanya (Open for all SANDEE@25 participants) Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room
12:30–13:30	Lunch
13:30–14:00	Conference kick-off Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room Opening Remarks Mani Nepal, Senior Programme Coordinator–SANDEE, ICIMOD Welcome Remarks Pema Gyamtsho, Director General, ICIMOD
14:00–15:30	Founder's keynote Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room Natural capital and the meaning of sustainable development Sir Partha Dasgupta, Frank Ramsey Professor Emeritus of Economics, Cambridge University, UK Moderator: Subhrendu K Pattanayak, Oak Professor of Environmental and Energy Policy, Duke University, USA
15:30 – 15:40	Book launch SANDEE@25: Reflections, lessons and memories of collective growth
15:40–16:15	Photo session Jitendra Raj Bajracharya, Photographer/ Photo Editor, ICIMOD Tea/coffee break
16:15–17:45	Reflections panel Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room Moderator: David Potter, Head of Regional Action and Global Advocacy, ICIMOD
17:45 – 18:00	SANDEE evaluation and tracer survey results Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room Ghulam Muhammad Shah , Impact Monitoring and Evaluation Specialist, ICIMOD
18:30–20:30	Reception dinner

End of Day 1

Day 02 | Saturday, 13 December 2025

Time (NPT)	Topic
08:30–09:00	Registration
09:00–10:15	<p>Keynote 02 Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room Our common(s) heritage: Contributions of development and environmental economics Ruth Meinzen-Dick, Senior Research Fellow Emeritus, IFPRI Moderator: E Somanathan, Professor, Economics and Planning Unit, Indian Statistical Institute</p>
10:15–11:00	<p>Keynote 03 Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room Bank lending in agricultural sector in Nepal: Issues and opportunities Biswo Nath Poudel, Governor, Nepal Rastra Bank Moderator: Mani Nepal, Senior Programme Coordinator – SANDEE, ICIMOD</p>
11:00–11:15	Tea/coffee break
Panel sessions A1 – A3	
11:15–12:45	<p>Panel A1 Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room Knowledge networks in times of climate change Moderator: Pranab Mukhopadhyay, Senior Professor, Goa University, India</p>
	<p>Panel A2 Hall: Rato Baithak Potential for scaling electric cooking in Nepal Moderator: E Somanathan, Professor, Economics and Planning Unit, Indian Statistical Institute, India</p>
	<p>Panel A3 Hall: Skyline Innovative financing for mountain ecosystem services: Strengthening PES mechanisms Moderator: Shweta Bhagwat, Senior Specialist – Nature-based Solutions and Climate Finance, IORA Ecological Solutions</p>
12:45–13:30	Lunch
Parallel Sessions A1 – A5	
13:30–15:00	<p>Parallel session A1 Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room Technology and sustainability in agriculture Chair: Soumya Balasubramaniya, Senior Economist, The World Bank Washington, USA</p>
	<p>Economic incentives for artificial intelligence-based digital technologies for sustainable agriculture Presenter: Madhu Khanna, Co-Director, Center for Economics of Sustainability University of Illinois, USA Discussant: Soumya Balasubramaniya, Senior Economist, The World Bank, Washington, USA</p>
	<p>Climate-smart agricultural innovations: Policy frameworks for adaptation, mitigation, and technology diffusion Presenter: V Saravanakumar, Professor, Agricultural Economics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India Discussant: Abid Hussain, Economics lead, ICIMOD</p> <p>Enhancing food security through food security of farmers: A look at how to implement commercial and organic farming among smallholder farmers Presenter: Tshotsho, Lecturer, Department of Sustainable Development, College of Natural Resources, Royal University of Bhutan, Bhutan Discussant: Pawan Kumar Sharma, Professor and Head of Department (Agricultural Economics), Sher-e-Kashmir University of, Agricultural Sciences & Technology of Jammu (J&K), India</p>

13:30–15:00	<p>Parallel session A2 Hall: Skyline Climate policies and livelihoods Chair: Sarala Khaling, Head of Resilient Economies and Landscapes, ICIMOD</p>
	<p>The public’s views on climate policies in seven large global south countries Presenter: Thomas Sterner, Professor, Environmental Economics, University of Gothenburg, Sweden Discussant: Ashish Tiwari, Air lead, ICIMOD</p>
	<p>Does climate vulnerability drive public health spending? Evidence from South and Southeast Asia (2000–2022) Presenter: Mohammad Iftekharul Islam, Research Associate, South Asian Network on Economic Modeling (SANEM), Dhaka, Bangladesh Discussant: Lubna Naz, Professor and Director, Center for Business and Economic Research (CBER), IBA, Karachi, Pakistan</p>
	<p>Climate risk and tribal livelihoods in central India: Assessment of institutional welfare schemes and tribal resilience Presenter: Mohanasundari Thangavel, Associate Professor, Indian Institute of Technology Indore, Madhya Pradesh, India Discussant: Sarala Khaling, Head of Resilient Economies and Landscapes, ICIMOD</p>
13:30–15:00	<p>Parallel session A3 Hall: The Regent Environmental sustainability: Methods and issues Chair: AK Enamul Haque, Director General, Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies (BIDS), Bangladesh</p>
	<p>Methodological issues in empirical research in environmental and development economics Presenter: Jean Marie Baland, Professor, Department of Economics, University of Namur, Belgium Discussant: AK Enamul Haque, Director General, Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies (BIDS), Bangladesh</p>
	<p>Trodding through environmental and sustainability issues since the 1990s: a reflection Presenter: Sajjad Zohir, Executive Director, Economic Research Group (ERG), Dhaka, Bangladesh Discussant: Heman Das Lohano, Visiting Professor, Department of Applied Economics, University of Minnesota, USA</p>
13:30–15:00	<p>Parallel session A4 Hall: Green Room Environmental health Chair: Bhim Adhikari, Senior Program Specialist, International Development Research Centre (IDRC), Canada</p>
	<p>A nature-based solution? Evaluating a health care provider nature exercise prescription using a pilot RCT data from rural Oregon, USA Presenter: Randall Bluffstone, Professor of Economics and Director, Institute for Economics and the Environment, Portland State University, USA Discussant: Pallab Mozumder, Department of Economics, Department of Earth and Environment, Florida International University, USA</p>
	<p>Society’s willingness to pay for less health risks by pesticide use: A case study Presenter: Prema A, Professor and Head, Department of Agricultural Economics, Kerala Agricultural University, India Discussant: Bhim Adhikari, Senior Program Specialist, International Development Research Centre (IDRC), Canada</p>
	<p>Can female leaders promote better health behaviour? Learning from a sanitation-and-hygiene communication experiment in rural Bangladesh Presenter: Atonu Rabbani, Professor, Department of Economics, University of Dhaka Discussant: Bishal Bharadwaj, Research Associate, Global Research Initiative, University of Calgary, Canada</p>

13:30–15:00	<p>Parallel session A5 Hall: Rato Baithak Forest and livelihoods Chair: Lucy Emerton, Director, Conservation Economics and Finance, Environment Management Group, Sri Lanka</p>
	<p>Effects of organised guarding on mortality from human-elephant conflict in Northeast India Presenter: E Somanathan, Professor, Economics and Planning Unit, Indian Statistical Institute, India Discussant: Lucy Emerton, Director, Conservation Economics and Finance, Environment Management Group, Sri Lanka</p>
	<p>Assessing the livelihood Impacts of non-governmental organisation-led forest restoration in village common forests: A case study Presenter: Md Shafiqul Bari, Vice-Chancellor, EXIM Bank Agricultural University Bangladesh, Bangladesh Discussant: Abul Kalam Azad, Senior Intervention Manager - Livelihoods and Enterprises, ICIMOD</p>
	<p>Government support for tree-growing by farmers: Evidence from India's agroforestry programmes Presenter: Chandan Singha, Associate Professor, Hindu College, University of Delhi, India Discussant: Prabath Nishantha Edirisinghe, Retired Conservator General of Forests, Department of Forest Conservation, Sri Lanka</p>
15:00–15:30	Tea/coffee break
15:30–17:00	Parallel sessions B1 – B5
15:30–17:00	<p>Parallel session B1 Hall: Skyline Forest conservation and management Chair: Jeffrey Vincent, Clarence F. Korstian Professor of Forest Economics and Management, Duke University, USA</p>
	<p>Community forest management: Unveiling the success story of Nepal Presenter: François Libois, Professor, Research Fellow and Professor, Paris School of Economics & Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement (INRAe), France Discussant: Jeffrey Vincent, Clarence F. Korstian Professor of Forest Economics and Management, Duke University, USA</p>
	<p>Dynamics of Community Forest User Group (CFUG) creation and spillover effects in Nepal's community forestry Presenter: Marine Gueben, PhD candidate, University of Namur, Belgium Discussant: Rajesh Kumar Rai, Professor, School of Forestry and Natural Resource Management, Tribhuvan University, Nepal</p>
	<p>What is a good mountain forest? and for whom? Presenter: Dil Bahadur Khatri, Executive Director and Senior Researcher, Southasia Institute of Advanced Studies (SIAS), Kathmandu, Nepal Discussant: Sony Baral, Assistant Dean, Institute of Forestry, Tribhuvan University, Nepal</p>
15:30–17:00	<p>Parallel session B2 Hall: Green Room Environmental valuation Chair: Ram Chandra Bhattarai, Associate Professor of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal</p>
	<p>Valuing the complementarity under integrated farming systems– the case of Pokkali Presenter: Indira Devi, Professor, Kerala Agricultural University, India Discussant: Ram Chandra Bhattarai, Associate Professor of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal</p>
	<p>Cleaner lakes at a price: Farmers' willingness to accept compensation for reducing chemical inputs in Myanmar's floating agriculture Presenter: Yarzar Hein, Professor and Head of Department, Advanced Center for Agricultural Research and Education, Myanmar Discussant: Kavita Sardana, Visiting Faculty of Economics, Ashoka University, India</p>
	<p>Consumers' preference and willingness to pay for Nepalese large cardamom in the global market Presenter: Rishi Ram Kattel, Professor, Agriculture and Forestry University (AFU), Nepal Discussant: Rajan Parajuli, Associate Professor, North Carolina State University, USA</p>

15:30–17:00	<p>Parallel session B3 (Hall: The Regent) Environmental Governance I Chair: Bishwa Nath Tiwari, Professor of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal</p>
	<p>Valuing ecosystem assets for ecosystem accounting in the Gunbower-Koondrook-Perricoota (GKP) forest icon site in Australia Presenter: Ram Pandit, Associate Professor, The University of Western Australia, Australia Discussant: Bishwa Nath Tiwari, Professor of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal</p>
	<p>Assessing tourism governance and ecological integration in mountain regions: Insights from Gilgit-Baltistan Presenter: Amjad Ali, Assistant Professor, Department of Development Studies, Karakoram International University, Pakistan Discussant: Muhammad Rafiq, Member (Climate Finance), Pakistan Climate Change Authority, Pakistan</p>
	<p>Beyond access: Institutional dynamics and farmer preferences in groundwater markets in semi-critical regions of India Presenter: Akshi Bajaj, Assistant Professor School of Business, University of Petroleum & Energy Studies (UPES), Dehradun Discussant: Eshita Gupta, Senior Economist, Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler (KPMG), Gurugram, India</p>
	<p>Can polycentric and adaptive approaches strengthen environmental governance in the Maldives? Presenter: Mohamed Shumais, The Maldives National University, Maldives Discussant: Niraj Prakash Joshi, Associate Professor, The International Development and Cooperation (IDEC) Institute, Hiroshima University, Japan</p>
15:30–17:00	<p>Parallel session B4 Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room Energy transition Chair: Shreekant Gupta, Professor, Delhi School of Economics, India</p>
	<p>Power sector for the developing Asian Regions by 2050: Modelling the strategic vision Presenter: Joyashree Roy, Distinguished Professor, Asian Institute of Technology (AIT), Thailand Discussant: Shreekant Gupta, Professor, Delhi School of Economics, India</p>
	<p>Can reliable electricity supply drive induction cooktop adoption? Evidence from a randomised experiment in Kathmandu Valley Presenter: Naveen Adhikari, Assistant Professor, Central Department of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal Discussant: Hari Katuwal, Associate Professor, Tarleton State University, USA</p>
	<p>Prepayment and electricity usage in temperature extremes: Implications for energy poverty and climate justice Presenter: Debasish Kumar Das, Lecturer in Economics, The University of New South Wales (UNSW), Canberra, Australia Discussant: Jin Yana, Assistant Professor of Environmental Economics and Policy, Peking University, China</p>
	<p>Response to Incentives to conserve electricity and household behaviour: Evidence from field experiment Presenter: Ngawang Dendup, Consultant (Economist), Asian Development Bank Institute (ADBI) Discussant: Santosh Adhikari, Assistant Professor and Programme Coordinator, Kathmandu University, Nepal</p>

15:30–17:00	Parallel session B5 Hall: Rato Baithak Climate change and agriculture Chair: Saudamini Das, Professor in Economics, Institute of Economic Growth, Delhi, India
	Do institutions, incentives, and information enhance adoption of climate-smart agriculture practices? Empirical evidence from India Presenter: Chandrasekhar Bahinipati, Head, Associate Professor, Indian Institute of Technology Tirupati, India Discussant: Mohammed Ziaul Haider, Professor, Economics Discipline, Khulna University, Bangladesh
	Crop diversification in a flood-affected landscape: Evidence from the Morigaon district of Assam, India Presenter: Monjit Borthakur, Assistant Professor, Department of Geography, Cotton University, India Discussant: Kishor Goswami, Professor of Economics, Indian Institute of Technology, (IIT) Kharagpur, India
	Land fragmentation and non-farm labour supply nexus: Evidence from Nepal Presenter: Prajjwal Dhungana, Research Associate, SANDEE, ICIMOD Discussant: Arjun Dhakal, Convener, Nepal Network for Social, Development, Economic and Environmental Dialogue (NNSDEE), Nepal

End of Day 2

Day 03 | 14 December 2025

Time (NPT)	Topic
08:30–09:00	Registration
09:00–10:30	Keynote 04 (Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room) Living in the age of adaptation: New challenges and new responsibilities for knowledge Adil Najam, President, Worldwide Fund for Nature (WWF) International Professor and Dean Emeritus, Boston University, USA Moderator: Jeffrey Vincent, Clarence F. Korstian Professor of Forest Economics and Management, Duke University, USA
10:30–10:45	Vote of thanks Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room David Potter , Head of Regional action and global advocacy, ICIMOD
10:45–11:00	Tea/coffee break
	Panel sessions B1 – B3
11:00–12:30	Panel B1 Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room The economics of springshed management and springs restoration in the Hindu Kush Himalaya (HKH) Moderator: Sarala Khaling, Head of Resilient Economies and Landscapes, ICIMOD
	Panel B2 Hall: Rato Baithak Harnessing big data and digital technologies for economic development in the HKH Moderator: Birendra Bajracharya, Interim Senior Intervention Manager – Regional information service, ICIMOD
	Panel B3 Hall: Skyline Landscape resource conservation for improving water availability, building climate resilience, and strengthening ecosystem services: Evidence from India Moderator: S Madheswaran, Professor and Head, Centre for Economic Studies and Policy, Institute for Social and Economic Change
12:30–13:30	Lunch

Parallel sessions C1 – C5	
13:30–15:00	Parallel session C1 Hall: The Regent Household energy choices Chair: Joyashree Roy, Distinguished Professor, Asian Institute of Technology (AIT), Thailand
	Leveraging local mass media: How FM stations amplify energy access and clean energy use in household Presenter: Bishal Bharadwaj, Research Associate, University of Calgary, Canada Discussant: Joyashree Roy, Distinguished Professor, Asian Institute of Technology (AIT), Thailand
	Nepal’s federal transition and rural household cooking fuel choice Presenter: Hari Katuwal, Associate Professor, Tarleton State University, USA Discussant: Krishna Prasad Pant, Visiting Faculty, Kathmandu University, Nepal
	Effects of transition from Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) to induction cookstoves in Kerala Anganwadis, India Presenter: Praveen Kumar, PhD, Senior Research Fellow Economics and Planning Unit, Indian Statistical Institute Delhi Discussant: Ngawang Dendup, Consultant (Economist), Asian Development Bank Institute (ADBI)
	Adopting solar power for irrigation: Implications for groundwater depletion in Gujarat Presenter: Praharsh M Patel, Assistant Professor, Indian Institute of Technology Gandhinagar, India Discussant: Indira Devi, Professor, Kerala Agricultural University, India
13:30–15:00	Parallel session C2 Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room Issues in water management Chair: Ramesh Ananda Vaidya, Fellow- Senior Advisor (Water and Energy), ICIMOD
	Groundwater use in South Asia: The role of technology and water-energy-food-poverty nexus trade-offs Presenter: Soumya Balasubramanya, Senior Economist, The World Bank, Washington DC, USA Discussant: Ramesh Ananda Vaidya, Fellow- Senior Advisor (Water and Energy), ICIMOD
	Urban household’s willingness to pay for improved water services Presenter: Niranjana Devkota, Research Fellow, Policy Research Institute, Government of Nepal Discussant: Yarzar Hein, Professor and Head of Department, Advanced Center for Agricultural Research and Education, Yezin Agricultural University, Myanmar
	Willingness to pay for domestic water in Meghalaya: Impact of water poverty and social structure Presenter: Rida Wanbha Nongbri, Research Scholar, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, India Discussant: Amjad Ali, Assistant Professor, Department of Development Studies, Karakoram International University Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan
13:30–15:00	Parallel session C3 Hall: Skyline Environmental governance and growth Chair: Shiva Raj Adhikari, Professor, Central Department of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal
	Discretionary enforcement and strategic compliance experimental evidence Presenter: Shreekanth Gupta, Professor, Delhi School of Economics, India Discussant: Resham B. Thapa-Parajuli, Associate Professor, Central Department of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal
	Towards sustainable industrialisation: The effects of eco-innovation in the environmental sustainability performance of the manufacturing Presenter: Sadia Islam, Assistant Professor, Dhaka School of Economics, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh Discussant: Mohamed Shumais, The Maldives National University, Maldives
	Stand characteristics in relation to forest management regimes and disturbance gradients in Tropical Forest Ecosystems Presenter: Mohammad Belal Uddin, Professor, Department of Forestry and Environmental Science, Shahjalal University of Science and Technology, Bangladesh Discussant: To Be Added

13:30–15:00	Parallel session C4 Hall: Rato Baithak Gender and energy transition Chair: Pranab Mukhopadhyay, Senior Professor, Goa University, India
	Electrifying empowerment: Women and energy access Presenter: Subhrendu Pattanayak, Professor, Environmental and Energy Policy, Duke University, USA Discussant: Atonu Rabbani, Professor, Department of Economics, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh
	Impact of indoor air pollution on child well-being Presenter: Heman Das Lohano, Visiting Professor, Department of Applied Economics, University of Minnesota, USA Discussant: Pranab Mukhopadhyay, Senior Professor, Goa University, India
	Women’s bargaining power and energy consumption in Myanmar Presenter: Zin Nwe Win, Country Manager, Sierra Leone and Liberia, Innovations for poverty action Discussant: Shiba Satyal Banskota, Gender Equality and Social Inclusion Lead, ICIMOD
13:30–15:00	Parallel session C5 Hall: Green Room Environmental pollution Chair: Bhupesh Adhikary, Climate Action Lead, ICIMOD
	Farmers’ preferences for different crop residue management practices: Evidence from choice experiment in Punjab, India Presenter: Eshita Gupta, Senior Economist, Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler (KPMG), Gurugram, India Discussant: Bhupesh Adhikary, Climate Action Lead, ICIMOD
	State mediated trade, distortions and air pollution Presenter: Digvijay Singh Negi, Associate Professor, Ashoka University, India Discussant: Mohammad Iftekharul Islam, Research Assistant, South Asian Network on Economic Modeling (SANEM)
	Fire in the fields, crime in the air Presenter: Hardeep Singh, Assistant Professor, Indian Institute of Technology Jammu, India Discussant: Tshotsho, Lecturer, College of Natural Resources, Royal University of Bhutan, Bhutan
15:00–15:30	Tea/coffee break
Parallel sessions D1–D5	
15:30–17:00	Parallel session D1 Hall: Himalaya Grand Ball Room Environmental governance II Chair: Yi Shaoliang, Senior Intervention Manager, Rangelands and wetlands, ICIMOD
	Empowering youth through engagement in environmental problem-solving: A case study of the Kutupalong Rohingya Refugee Camp in Bangladesh Presenter: Rumi Shammin, David Orr Professor, Environmental Studies and Sciences Program, Oberlin College, USA Discussant: Yi Shaoliang, Senior Intervention Manager, Rangelands and wetlands, ICIMOD
	Assessing well-being and sustainability of small-scale fishing communities in Nepal Presenter: Thaneshwar Bhandari, Assistant Professor Institute of Agriculture and Animal Science, Tribhuvan University, Nepal Discussant: Indrila Guha, Principal and Head of Department, Department of Economics, Basanti Devi College, India
	Clean fuel use, political representation and forest cover: Evidence from rural India Presenter: Prasenjit Sarkhel, Professor, Department of Economics, University of Kalyani, India Discussant: Monjit Borthakur, Assistant Professor, Department of Geography, Cotton University, Assam, India

15:30–17:00	<p>Parallel session D2 Hall: Skyline Climate adaptation and mitigation Chair: Randall Bluffstone, Professor of Economics and Director of the Institute for Economics and the Environment, Portland State University, USA</p>
	<p>A cross-country and long-term evaluation of United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) climate change adaptation projects Presenter: Saudamini Das, Professor in Economics, Institute of Economic Growth, India Discussant: David Potter, Head of Regional Action and Global Advocacy, ICIMOD</p>
	<p>Quantifying non-economic losses and damages in Sindh post 2022 floods Presenter: Lubna Naz, Professor and Director, Center for Business and Economic Research, Institute of Business Administration Karachi, Pakistan Discussant: Randall Bluffstone, Professor of Economics and Director of the Institute for Economics and the Environment, Portland State University, USA</p>
	<p>Perceived adverse impacts undermine limited socio-economic benefits of resin tapping from Chirpine forests Presenter: Rajan Parajuli, Associate Professor, North Carolina State University, USA Discussant: Kishor Atreya, Associate Professor, Institute of Forestry, Tribhuvan University, Nepal</p>
	<p>The rapid economic recovery from earthquake relief to reconstruction: A case study of the 7 January 2025 Dingri earthquake, Xizang, China Presenter: Bingwei Tian, Associate Professor, Assistant Dean, PhD, The Institute for Disaster Management and Reconstruction (IDMR), Sichuan University, China Discussant: Nirmal Kumar Raut, Associate Professor, Central Department of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal</p>
15:30:15–17:00	<p>Parallel session D3 Hall: The Regent Topics in environmental economics I Chair: Jón Geir Pétursson, Professor Environment and Natural Resources, Interdisciplinary Graduate Programme, University of Iceland, Iceland</p>
	<p>Climate variability and household electricity consumption Presenter: Rosalina Palanca-Tan, Professor, Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines Discussant: Jón Geir Pétursson, Professor Environment and Natural Resources, Interdisciplinary Graduate Programme, University of Iceland, Iceland</p>
	<p>Macroeconomic analysis of green monetary policy in India's emission mitigation: Evidence from Wallace neutrality Presenter: Sayar Ahmad Shah, PhD Scholar, Indian Institute of Technology of Ropar, India Discussant: V Saravanakumar, Professor, Agricultural Economics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India</p>
	<p>Do international remittances enhance credit repay ability and reshape labour supply among households with international migrants in Nepal? Presenter: Sumant Kumar Yadav, master's student, Hiroshima University, Japan Discussant: Gopal Tiwari, General Secretary of Nepal Economic Association</p>

15:30–17:00	Parallel session D4 Hall: Green Room Natural disasters Chair: Orapan Srisawalak, Professor Emeritus, Sukhothai Thammathirat Open University, Thailand
	Impact of climatic shocks and coping strategies on livelihood: Evidence from the coastal Bangladesh Presenter: Pallab Mozumder, Associate Professor, Florida International University, USA Discussant: Orapan Srisawalak, Professor Emeritus, Sukhothai Thammathirat Open University, Thailand
	Paved to nowhere: The dubious payoffs of Nepal’s rural road expansion Presenter: Santosh Adhikari, Assistant Professor and Program Coordinator, Kathmandu University, Nepal Discussant: Raghu Bir Bista, Associate Professor, Department of Economics, Tribhuvan University, Nepal
	When the rain stops, do rings come early? Rainfall shocks and child marriage in Nepal Presenter: Adish Karki, undergrad student (Senior), Kathmandu University, Nepal Discussant: Ratna Kumar Jha, Research fellow, Food and Agriculture Organization, United Nations, Nepal
	Shadows of shock: Natural disasters and the dynamics of economic growth and recovery in South Asian countries Presenter: Abina VP, PhD Scholar, Institute for Social and Economic Change, India Discussant: Ridish Pokharel, Professor of Forestry, Tribhuvan University, Nepal
15:30–17:00	Parallel session D5 Hall: Rato Baithak Topics in environmental economics II Chair: Gunnar Köhlin, Associate Professor, School of Business, Economics and Law, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden
	SANDEE family from Pakistan@2025: Achievements and leadership development in environment economics Presenter: Khuda Bakhsh, Professor, Cotton University, India Discussant: Gunnar Köhlin, Associate Professor, School of Business, Economics and Law, University of Gothenburg, Sweden
	Effectiveness of fiscal policy for forest conservation and restoration in Indian States Presenter: Amarendra Das, Associate Professor, National Institute of Science Education and Research (NISER), India Discussant: EPN Udayakumara, Professor, Sabaragamuwa University of Sri Lanka
	Consumers’ attitude towards food waste reduction and projecting its econo-environmental benefits Presenter: Tasnim Murad Mamun, Associate Professor, Economics Discipline, Khulna University, Bangladesh Discussant: Yamini Gupt, Professor, University of Delhi, India
	Demand for clean air increases with pollution abatement success Presenter: Jin Yana, Assistant Professor, Peking University, China Discussant: Chandan Singha, Associate Professor, Hindu College, University of Delhi, India

End of Day 3 and the conference

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